

Deliverable 5.7 Networking activity reports

EURAKNOS

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

TASK 5.3

Summary

The overall aim of WP5 is to widen and maximize the (possible) impact of the EURAKNOS project through communication, dissemination and by proactively carrying out networking activities. The specific objectives of WP5 are to:

- Develop a detailed and dynamic communication plan;
- Progress a detailed and dynamic communication and exploitation plan, respectively;
- Efficiently communicate the EURAKNOS concept, progress and results to a wide variety of actors;
- Disseminate the EURAKNOS outputs focusing on the following two groups of actors: 1. Thematic Network coordinators as multipliers and 2. foresters and farmers as end-users;
- Provide a wide range of materials targeted at end-users;
- Link to educational programmes and training initiatives;
- Promote Cross-Exchange between various Thematic Networks

Task 5.3 on networking focuses on the EURAKNOS project working closely with other projects or initiatives, which are investigating aspects of a similar nature, whether led by industry, researchers, national or EU policymakers. A Networking Plan, functioning as a midterm networking report (D5.3) has been developed, which the current deliverable builds on. Also, task 5.3 on networking serves as an example of how to perform networking for other Thematic Networks. The work has focused on proactively engaging in networking activities with other Thematic Networks as well as actors at both national, regional and international level.

Based on the networking strategy, three types of networking activities were targeted: 1. Activities related to Thematic Networks and their networks, including Operational Groups and other H2020 MAPS, 2. Activities with similar initiatives or organizations with a common interest at regional, national, European and International level, 3. Activities with educational programmes and training initiatives. For each type of networking activity, individual targets were identified with related estimated target figures (number of events) and outreach (number of participants at events).

Throughout the lifetime of the project, in total, partners have been participating in 74 events where networking activities have been carried out. The 74 events include 17 Cross Exchange Visits. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the networking activities taking place during the last year of the project period were changed to online meetings, workshops and conferences. Planned participation in four events, led by third party, was not carried out due to three events being postponed and one event cancelled, all due to COVID-19.

The majority of target estimates related to the various networking activities have been reached. In particular, this is the case for activities related to Thematic Networks and their networks and for activities with similar initiatives or organizations with a common interest. Thus, the networking outreach has been successful with a reach of more than 1800 participants. Less success was obtained regarding activities with educational programmes and training initiatives.

A Policy Brief has been developed (presented in D5.9), which aims to provide policy makers with recommendations (6 main recommendations), in order to create an enabling environment for establishing Thematic Networks and to ensure their stability. The Policy Brief has been published in the Open Access Project Repository Journal 8 January 2021: [Policy Brief](#). The Policy Brief is also

available on the EURAKNOS website: [Policy Brief](#). A Vision Paper (presented in D5.8) has been developed on the future of knowledge reservoirs in agriculture and forestry. It is available on the EURAKNOS website: [Vision Paper](#).

The Communication and Dissemination/Exploitation reports must also be taken into consideration to get a full view of the reach of the EURAKNOS project.

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	E	Ethics	

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

AKIS	– Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
BSc	– Bachelor of Science
CAP	– Common Agricultural Policy
CEJA	– European Council of Young Farmers
COPA-COGECA	– European Farmers - European Agri-Cooperatives
DG-AGRI	– Directorate General Agriculture and Rural Development
EIP-AGRI	– The agricultural European Innovation Partnership
EUFRAS	– European Forum for Agricultural and Advisory Services
EURAKNOS	– Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs: towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System
EUREKA	– European Knowledge Repository for Best Agricultural Practices
FAO	– Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations
FERTINNOWA – a TN	– Transfer of Innovative Techniques for Sustainable Water Use in Fertigated Crops
GODAN	– Global Open Data for Agriculture & Nutrition
HIKR	– High Impact Knowledge Reservoir
IN	– Innovation Network
KIP	– Knowledge Innovation Panel
KR	– Knowledge Reservoir
MA	– Multi-Actor
MAP	– Multi-Actor Project
MS	– Member States
MSc	– Master of Science
NARIC	– National Agricultural Research and Innovation Centre
NGO	– Non-Governmental Organisation
NRN	– National Rural Network
OG	– Operational Group
PhD	– Doctor of Philosophy
SCAR SWG AKIS	– Standing Committee on Agricultural Research Strategic Working group on Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
SIB	– Strategic Innovation Board
TN	– Thematic Network
WP	– Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

1.1.1. Project overview

EURAKNOS (www.euraknos.eu/) is a Thematic Network (TN) created with the aim to collate knowledge from all TNs to build a single community. TNs have the potential to maximise the uptake and impact of new knowledge by stimulating shared learning and coordinating the dissemination of practical information. The overall aim of the EURAKNOS project is to strengthen the EU agricultural knowledge base by co-creating “the network to connect all thematic networks”.

The main objectives of EURAKNOS are to:

- Develop technical guidelines for building a successful TN based on the multi-actor approach;
- Define best dissemination practices (tools, materials, channels...) with high impact on the end-users in particular farmers, foresters and advisors;
- To develop a pilot for an open-access EU wide agricultural knowledge innovation system.

In order to achieve these objectives, EURAKNOS will:

- Facilitate and support thematic networks, link similar initiatives at EU and national levels and feed into national educational and training programmes;
- Widen and connect existing thematic networks to build knowledge reservoirs within the agricultural European Innovation Partnership (EIP-AGRI);
- Collect, evaluate and compare knowledge, materials and tools that have been produced by thematic networks and operational groups;
- Develop a harmonised approach by producing technical guidelines on how to make a high-impact knowledge reservoir;
- Develop a blueprint for creating an EU-wide, dynamic, open-source agricultural knowledge innovation database, and explore the value of doing this.

1.1.2. Networking: Definition, aim and impact

A definition of networking is non-existing in the EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms. However, in the publication ‘Making the Most of your H2020 Project’¹, it is stated that as part of communication, the project should:

‘Use existing resources in your consortium to increase outreach on international, national, and regional level – for example, rely on your project partners’ already existing contacts and networks ...’.

According to the Merriam Webster Dictionary² networking is:

‘The exchange of information or services among individuals, groups, or institutions’.

¹ https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/EU-IPR-Brochure-Boosting-Impact-C-D-E_0.pdf

² <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/networking>

The aim of WP5 is to widen the (possible) impact of TNs knowledge reservoirs, thus, the work in WP5 focuses on communication, dissemination and networking of the EURAKNOS project. The relation between WP5 and other WPs in the EURAKNOS project is presented in Figure 1. Communication and disseminations are closely linked to networking (see Figure 1). Also, the networking performed in EURAKNOS has been to use the communication and dissemination materials at occasions where project partners are in direct interaction with the relevant networking partners, e.g. TN's and initiatives with a common interest. Thus, on several occasions, communication and/or dissemination and networking are closely intertwined, and networking is a way of promoting communication and dissemination. At the same time, communication and dissemination create materials to include in networking activities.

The expected outcome of the project, including networking activities, is to raise the impact of TNs through connecting them, and guiding the first steps towards a standardised approach and a pilot for an open-access EU wide knowledge reservoir for agriculture and forestry. The aim of the Networking Activities is to help the EURAKNOS project learn from other ongoing initiatives and projects and then share results of EURAKNOS based on findings within the TN community and beyond. This will bring the research closer to the practice and share innovative knowledge and best practices to the largest extent possible with farmers and foresters throughout the EU.

Figure 1: Links between Work Packages (WPs) in the EURAKNOS Project with Network activities in WP5

1.1.3. Networking: Tasks

Task 5.3 on networking has relied on the EURAKNOS project working closely with other projects or initiatives, which were investigating aspects of a similar nature, whether led by industry, researchers, national or EU policymakers. This is to ensure that the outputs of the EURAKNOS project draw on the findings from other projects and, in turn, inform these, and other future research and innovation projects and policy development processes – in short, that is to bring people together to gather and share useful information.

Projects currently funded under H2020 and future calls as well as Operational Groups (OGs) linked to the national and regional implementation of EIP Agri, also provided a clear scope for complementarity and networking.

The current deliverable is based on the initiatives and work, as also presented in the Networking plan with the following objectives:

- Outline a coherent networking strategy with a timeline
- Establish management and monitoring of networking activities
- Ensure that networking activities are carried out
- Collaborate with relevant initiatives and activities in EURAKNOS
- Plan networking activities with clear links to other WPs and their outputs, e.g. surveys, and plan how to organise joint meetings as well as other joint activities with projects relevant for the outcome of both projects
- Define measurable indicators to evaluate the success of networking activities

This deliverable on Networking activity reports presents the networking activities carried out throughout the entire length of the EURAKNOS project as an example of how to carry out networking in other TN's.

2. Task members

Below is presented an overview of the partners involved in WP5 (Table 1).

Table 1. Partners involved in the different Tasks of WP5 (in bold "L" the task leaders)

Task	Partner																
	ACTA	IDELE	NAK	UGent	GLZ	USC	AU	PSKW	ARC	AUA	IFA	LFG	RAU	EV ILVO	IFV	NAIK	IFOAM-EU
5.1	L	X	X			X					X		X				
5.2		X	X			X		X			L		X				
5.3		X	X		X	X	L	X			X		X				
5.4	X	X	X		L		X	X	X		X		X				X
WP ¹				X						X		X*		X	X	X*	

¹Budget not allocated to the task

*Originally no budget but was involved after the amendment

3. Methodology

3.1. Networking targets

Networking activities were targeted at several levels:

- TN coordinators and TN communities (TN partners and their networks)
- Other MA H2020 projects and OGs
- Similar initiatives/projects at regional, national, and international level (GODAN, FAO, NRNs)
- Institutions or organisations with a common interest at regional, national, European and international level, including local authorities and policymakers

 Vocational schools, educational institutions, advisor training initiatives, and lifelong learning programmes.

Regarding networking targeted towards educational and training programmes and initiatives, each partner provided a list of relevant:

- Educational institutions for networking at national and/or EU level and/or within their expertise, described by the main focus, country, type of school, number of students, the longevity of curriculum etc.;
- Advisor training programmes in own country and/or within their expertise described by the main focus, country, type of school, number of students, the longevity of course;
- Universities in their own country and/or within their expertise, described by the main focus, country, type of education, number of students, the longevity of education (BSc, MSc, PhD), etc.

The networking activities were carried out throughout the length of the project and was initiated already in the planning of the project and the process of conceptualization.

A SIB (Strategic Innovation Board) was established to accompany the progress of the EURAKNOS project, advice on project execution, dissemination and training needs, and support the consortium in the advocacy of EURAKNOS policy recommendations. Also, the SIB provided strategic advice to the project to maximise the outreach to end-users (farmers and foresters, and advisers). The SIB worked closely with the Management Board (MB) through meetings and workshops. The strategic advice from the SIB was based on links with national, regional and international initiatives, and the output of the assessments of the KIP (Knowledge Innovation Panel). Regularly, the SIB interacted with the Project Coordinator and the MB in order to give continuous feedback on the research approaches regarding the generation of exploitable results and recommendations. Thus, The SIB was the main source of neutral advice for the project.

SIB members were selected based on their level of expertise to be able to provide strategic advice during the project, on the international and European wide organisations and/or the institutions they represented in the scope of networking activities with similar goals and/or common interests. Furthermore, the selection was based on having similar initiatives/projects at the regional, national, and international level (GODAN, FAO, NRNs), and whether they came from institutions or organisations with a common interest at the regional, national, European and international level, including local authorities and policymakers.

The KIP consisted of experts from international organisations such as FAO and OECD, European farmer and advisors organisations such as EUFRAS, CEJA, and COPA COGECA. The aim was that the KIP constituted representatives of different organisations (NGOs, government agencies, chambers of agriculture, extension services, and research organisations, with a strong core group of end-users). The KIP assisted the EURAKNOS project in terms of assessing and evaluating existing networks, to work towards a harmonised approach, best format, tools, as well as ways to collect and disseminate knowledge oriented to the needs of end-users. Regularly, the KIP was consulted on a modular basis through workshops, surveys and working group (WG) meetings (selected KIP members for selected activities).

KIP members were selected by the EURAKNOS partners in collaboration with WP1 (Task 1.3), also based on their level of expertise and their affiliation. To enhance the networking and widening within the TN community, all TN coordinators and TN communities not included in the EURAKNOS consortium were included in the KIP.

Prior to the first assembly of the EURAKNOS kick-off meeting, a definite and additional selection of candidates for the SIB and SIB was made based on their added value to the project. All EURAKNOS partners were asked to point out a representative from their own country or candidates for involvement in other projects. During the project period, the list of KIP members was expanding.

3.2. Networking Activities

Networking is separated from communication or dissemination by the fact that they have a direct goal of transferring information or output from the project, whereas networking is a mutual interaction, where both parties give and receive input. Usually, networking is informal, e.g. sharing experiences during breaks at events, where people exchange information about their activities, and maybe share cards with contact information. Thus, often networking was carried out at events/activities where the EURAKNOS project partners were attending but were officially representing other organizations and initiatives.

According to the various target groups, the networking activities were divided into three main categories:

- Networking activities with TNs and their networks including OGs and other H2020 MAPs. Direct networking about EURAKNOS with other TNs can lead to indirect networking via the TN to their networks. The activities were targeted towards developing a “best practice networking plan” to support other TNs and projects to do their own networking.
- Networking activities with similar initiatives and/or organisations/institutions with a common interest at regional, national, European and international level (e.g. databases developed by NRNs, local authorities, FAO, GODAN, EUFRAS, etc.);
- Networking activities with educational programs and training initiatives (e.g. vocational schools, universities, technical schools, farmers and advisor training initiative, lifelong learning programmes) e.g. informing about EURAKNOS’ activities and including in workshops, KIP, etc.

3.3. Key point indicators (Horizon 2020 definition³)

In order to measure possible impact EURAKNOS provides qualitative and quantitative indicators. They are defined as the measurement of an objective to be met, a resource mobilised, an effect obtained, or a context variable. Output indicators relate to the specific results of the intervention. Thus, outputs generally occur within the short to medium term. Indicators of output (the result) represent the immediate effects of the measure concerned and look at its direct addressees. Impact indicators represent what the successful long term outcome should be in terms of impact on the economy/society beyond those directly affected by the intervention. Impact broadly defines the wider societal, economic, or environmental cumulative changes over a longer period. Thus, the KPI are mainly output and can be measured within the lifespan of the project.

3.4. Networking strategy

The final Networking activity report gives a detailed outline of the whole project period including the extended project period and reports on all activities (M0-M27). Initially, for each type of networking activity, relevant projects/initiatives and targets were identified (see Table 2). For each type of the three networking activities, networking measures and activities with related quantitative indicators

³ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/call_ptef/pt/2018-2020/h2020-call-pt-ria-ia-2018-20_en.pdf

were identified. For each of the quantitative indicators, estimated target numbers were set that refers to the number of events we aimed at reaching. The number related to networking targets reached refers to how many people we aimed at reaching.

Table 2: Overview of the EURAKNOS Networking Strategy including types of networking activities, target groups, networking measures and activities and quantitative indicators. The targets and networking measures and activities represents the target groups for the EURAKNOS project and the activities the EURAKNOS project aimed at participating in. Quantitative indicators with estimated target numbers represent the number of people the project aimed at reaching out to.

Type of networking activity	Target	Networking measures and activities	Quantitative indicators (with estimated target numbers, no)
Networking activities related to TNs and the networks of the TNs including OGs and other H2020 MAPS	TN coordinators and TN community (TN partners and their networks), OGs, end-user groups, H2020 MAPs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in surveys/interviews • Joint participatory workshops and bilateral meetings • New articles & podcasts on TNs used for networking • Cross exchange visits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joint workshops (6) • Bilateral meetings (28) • Cross-exchange visits (15) • Networking targets reached (100)
Networking activities with similar initiatives or organisations with a common interest at the regional, national, European & international level	NRNs, Innovation Networks, FAO, GODAN, EUFRAS, Copa-Cogeca, OECD, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SIB meetings • Participation in EIP - AGRI seminars • Participation in SCAR SWG AKIS meetings • Participation in international meetings • Participation in EUFRAS meetings • Policy brief on the future of TNs • Vision paper on an open-source knowledge reservoir (KR) for agriculture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SIB meetings (4) • Participation in EIP-AGRI seminars (4) • Participation in SWG AKIS meetings (4) • Participations in EUFRAS meetings (2) • Networking targets reached (50)
Networking activities with educational programs and training initiatives	Vocational schools, educational institutions, advisor training initiatives, lifelong learning programmes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in workshops • Bilateral contacts/meetings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participations in workshops (10) • Bilateral contacts/meetings (15)

3.5 Networking Management and Monitoring

3.5.1. Management

Partners were informed at the second consortium meeting (Athens, June 17-18, 2019), at the mid-term consortium meeting (Bruges, January 30-31, 2020 and online Consortium webinar, June 15-17, 2020), and at the final consortium meeting (Online, February 25, 2021) about their obligations related to networking. From task leader (AU/ICROFS), this included informing partners about what networking

is, being proactive on networking, be aware of when it is taking place, recording networking, as well as informing partners about the progress of recording. Additionally, regularly, and in the final year of the project meetings were carried out once a month, online meetings took place where partners in task 5.3 were informed about the progress of networking and reminded about obligations concerning networking.

3.5.2. Monitoring

To obtain an overview of the networking activities, an excel spreadsheet was created and uploaded on SharePoint for partners to record networking events. For each networking event, partners filled in a networking activity report with the following information: date, name of the event, location, number of external participants, number of external partners involved, type of stakeholders represented, highlights of the networking activity at the event and 1-2 pictures from the event if possible. The networking activity reports are listed in Annex I, which is provided as a supplement to the deliverable.

4. Content / results

4.1. Networking targets

In chapter three, the SIB and KIP were presented. To recap, The SIB and KIP is a dynamic list of experts that were consulted at workshops, through surveys or interviews as an integral part of the EURAKNOS TN. The SIB consisted of eight external representatives of various European and international organizations active in the domain of the EURAKNOS objectives. The KIP consisted of representatives located in 21 different MS (Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, The Netherlands, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, and Sweden) as well as UK and Switzerland. More details about the KIP actor's composition are available in Figure 2. The list of KIP members expanded during the project as new contacts were created and summed up to approx. 140 members at the end of the project. Half of the KIP members were end-users (farmers, foresters, and advisors). The following organisations/institutions were represented in the SIB and KIP:

1) The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO):

The Family Farming Knowledge Platform⁴ under FAO gathers digitized quality information on family farming from all over the world; including national laws and regulations, public policies, best practices, relevant data and statistics, research, articles, and publications.

2) Global Open Data for Agriculture & Nutrition (GODAN)⁵:

An international initiative that seeks to support global efforts to make agricultural and nutritionally relevant data available, accessible, and usable for unrestricted use worldwide. The initiative focuses on building high-level policy, and public and private institutional support for open data.

3) European Forum for Agricultural and Advisory Services (EUFRAS)⁶:

A European network and representative association of public and private rural and agricultural extension services that is aligned to the global representative body for advisory services [GFRAS](http://www.gfras.eu) with associations set up within many other continents.

4) European Rural Development Network (ERDN)⁷:

⁴ <http://www.fao.org/family-farming/background/en/>

⁵ <https://www.godan.info/pages/mission>

⁶ <http://www.eufRAS.eu/index.php/about-us>

⁷ <https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/>

Dates back to 2002 and was established to integrate the efforts and competencies of various European research institutions in their joint works on the state and paths of the transformation of rural areas, in particular farming, with a view to the extension of the EU and its future policies. Thus, the main objectives of the ERDN are parallel to the Community's idea of building the European Research Area for agriculture and rural development. The Network is meant to encompass the leading research centers studying rural development in Europe, and in particular in its Central, Eastern and South-Eastern countries.

5) Directorate General Agriculture and Rural Development (DG-AGRI)⁸:

This Commission department is responsible for EU policy in agriculture and rural development and deals with all aspects of the common agricultural policy (CAP).

6) National Agricultural and Innovation Centre (NAIK)⁹-AK:

National Agricultural Research and Innovation Centre, NARIC was founded by the governmental act 1476 (VII.24.), on January 1, 2014. An integrated, single legal entity was established from the sectoral governmental RDI capacities (13 research institutes in the field of agriculture and food science), where the institutes keep their professional autonomy as separate organizational units and their financial management is carried out on a high level of independence.

7) European Farmers- European Cooperatives (Copa-Cogeca)¹⁰: Is the united voice of farmers and their cooperatives in the European Union, they established the EU Code of Conduct on agricultural data sharing¹¹.

8) European Council of Young Farmers (CEJA)¹²: CEJA is a forum for dialogue between Europe's next generation of farmers and key decision-makers.

⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/info/departments/agriculture-and-rural-development_en

⁹ <https://www.naik.hu/en/organizations/national-agricultural-research-and-innovation-centre>

¹⁰ <https://www.copa-cogeca.eu/Menu.aspx>

¹¹ https://www.copa-cogeca.eu/img/user/files/EU%20CODE/EU_Code_2018_web_version.pdf

¹² <https://www.ceja.eu/home>

Figure 2: Actor composition of the Knowledge Innovation Panel: 140 members including TN coordinators and experts from various groups of actors.

In addition, networking between EURAKNOS and between TN coordinators and TN communities, and their networks took place throughout the duration of the project, giving two-way interaction of input from TNs to EURAKNOS and output from EURAKNOS to be used by the TNs. As an example, Figure 3 illustrates the consortium and network of the TN OK-Net-Arable.

Figure 3: Partners of the OK-Net-Arable Thematic Network (TN).
Black circles represent the project partners, green circles the practice partners.

From the conceptualization phase of the project and onwards, contacts with target networking partners in the KIP and SIB were established and the KIP was continuously expanded through new contacts with up to 140 members.

Additionally, EURAKNOS has collaborated with the **SCAR SWG AKIS** via partners that are members (UGent, ARC, USC, and IFOAM-EU). A Policy Brief (D5.9) has been produced in cooperation with the SCAR SWG AKIS to create awareness on the EURAKNOS output to policymakers, advisory groups, decision-making bodies, etc. Also, a vision paper has been produced with the Strategic Innovation Board (SIB) to produce a vision for the future of open-source Knowledge Reservoirs (KRs) in agriculture and forestry practice

Cross Exchange Visits (CEVs) were carried out in task 5.4 with other MA H2020 projects and OGs, and or with institutions or organisations with a common interest at regional, national, European and international level. They are by default networking and were reported as such.

4.2. Networking timeline

In total, 74 networking events were reported and of these, 17 events were CEV's carried out during the last year of the project. Besides, in the conceptualisation phase of the EURAKNOS project, one networking activity took place at the FERTINOWA Final Conference (October 2018) before the start of the project. Number 36 and 37 were not used during the process of reporting and is not available in Annex I, thus, these do not represent events that were cancelled nor postponed. In some cases, networking reports contain a limited amount of information, as it was not possible to obtain further

data about the activity. This is evident from table 3, as the number of events do not correspond with the number of networking activity reports.

Below is presented a timeline for the networking activities carried out during the entire length of the project (Figure 4-6). The number of networking activities, including CEVs, carried out by the different partners is presented in Table 3.

4.2.1. Implications of COVID-19

Three planned networking activities were postponed past the end date of the project due to the COVID-19 pandemic: SCAR SWG AKIS on social innovation (networking activity report no 29), AKIS conference (networking activity report no. 32), and EIP-AGRI seminar on CAP strategic plans and the key role of AKIS member states (networking activity report no 35). One event was cancelled due to the COVID-19: Copa-Cogeca 'H2020 Thematic Networks in Agricultural Innovation' (networking activity report no 38). These events are not indicated in the timeline figure.

The planned workshop in Tallinn with the participation of the KIP was converted to seven online webinars (activities no. 39, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46). From the end of March 2020, in total, 42 events where networking activities were planned, were converted from physical meetings or conferences to online meetings or webinars. All CEV were carried out during the time of the COVID-19 pandemic. Thus, they were converted to online meetings. The networking activities targeted at specific events were successfully carried out. However, at events where the project itself was not the focus, networking during breaks is less likely to have taken place compared to physical meetings. When arranging online meetings or webinars it has been a learning process to stimulate networking with the functions available in online tools. As project partners and participants became more experienced in online meetings and webinars, also skills in online networking improved.

Figure 4: Timeline and overview of networking activities (date, networking event, and place), that were carried out during the first year (2019) of the EURAKNOS project. Number in parenthesis indicate the corresponding networking activity report presented in Annex I.

Figure 5: Timeline and overview of networking activities (date, networking event, and place) carried out during the second year (2020) of the EURAKNOS project. Number in parenthesis indicate corresponding networking activity report presented in Annex I.

Figure 6 Timeline and overview of networking activities (date, event name, and place) carried out during the first three months of 2021. Number in parenthesis indicate networking activity report presented in Annex I.

Table 3: Overview of the number of networking activities including Cross Exchange Visits (CEV) and the corresponding network activity reports carried out and reported by each partner. Some of the events have two responsible partners; in these cases the event has been reported for both partners

WP5	Total number of networking events	Total number of networking reports	CEV (no)	CEV report filled in (no)
IFA	5	5	1	1
GLZ	7	4	2	2
ACTA	2	2	1	1
AU	10	10	1	1
RAU	2	2	2	2
NAK	2	1	2	n.a.
IDELE	4	4	1	1
USC	4	4	1	1
PSKW	2	1	2	2
ARC	2	2	1	1
IFOAM	1	1	2	2
Ugent	20	15	1	1
AUA	4	4		
IFV	2	2	1*	1
EV ILVO			1**	1
LFG	1	1		
NAIK				
Total	68	58	17	15

*CEV was carried out together with ACTA (not included in total amount of CEV)

**CEV was carried out together with UGent (not included in total amount of CEV).

5. Discussion

Below is presented an overview of the quantitative indicators for the various types of networking activities and the corresponding numbers reached out to in relation to the estimated number (Table 4). For presentation of the results of the CEVs see Table 5. For the planning and preparations of the CEVs see D5.4.

Regarding activities related to TNs and the networks of TNs, the estimated target numbers have been reached. The same applies to activities with similar initiatives or organisations with common interests.

Table 4 Overview of the EURAKNOS Networking outreach including types of networking activities, quantitative indicators, estimated target numbers, and reached numbers of participants/activities/events. The number of targets reached represents the number of persons participating in the activities/events

Type of networking activity	Quantitative indicators	Estimated target numbers	Reached numbers
Networking activities related to TNs and the networks of the TNs including OGs and other H2020 MAPS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of joint workshops • Number of bilateral meetings • Number of cross-exchange visits • Number of networking targets reached 	<p>6</p> <p>28</p> <p>15</p> <p>100</p>	<p>11</p> <p>31</p> <p>17</p> <p>>750</p>
Networking activities with similar initiatives or organisations with a common interest at the regional, national, European & international level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of SIB meetings • Number of participation in EIP-AGRI seminars • Participation in SWG AKIS meetings • Number of participations in EUFRAS meetings • Number of networking targets reached 	<p>4</p> <p>4</p> <p>4</p> <p>2</p> <p>50</p>	<p>2</p> <p>4</p> <p>5</p> <p>1</p> <p>150</p>
Networking activities with educational programs and training initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of participations in workshops • Number of bilateral contacts/meetings 	<p>10</p> <p>15</p>	<p>1</p> <p>MA-Survey</p>

Table 5 Overview of Cross exchange visits (CEVs) performed by partners including date, purpose, and representatives participating

Executing institution	CEV date	CEV purpose	Format (webinar/workshop)	Participants in total	Euraknos representatives	KIP representatives	SIB representatives	TN representatives	OG representatives	advisors/intermediaries	practitioners agriculture/forestry	other non-categorized
IFA	09-09-2020	Exploring how the tools and knowledge gathered by TNs and other projects can more effectively influence end-users at the farm-level through improved user-engagement, impact and sustainability.	webinar/online workshop	40	2	0	0	10	0	28	0	0
GLZ	09-10-2020	Potential of digital events for future TNs and Ogs on the example of a real webinar.	webinar	9	2	0	0	5	0	1	1	0
GLZ	16-06-2020	Discuss best practices about peer to peer learning, communication and dissemination and impact measuring.	webinar	15	1	0	0	1	0	0	13	0
IFV/ACTA	30-06-2020	How to foster peer to peer exchange in viticulture	webinar	12	3	0	0	9	0	0		0
ICROFS	19-11-2020	Exchange of knowledge on networking, including networking online	Workshop (online)	13	2	0	0	9	0	0	0	
RAU	17-sep-20	Presentation of EURAKNOS and its findings on facilitating farmer led innovation and panel discussion to share learnings	webinar	26	8	2	0	2	0	8	6	8

Executing institution	CEV date	CEV purpose	Format (webinar/ workshop)	Participants in total	Euraknos representatives	KIP representatives	SIB representatives	TN representatives	OG representatives	advisors/ intermediaries	practitioners agriculture/ forestry	other non-categorized
RAU	22-sep-20	Presentation of EURAKNOS and its findings on mobilising networks and panel discussion to share learnings	webinar	18	5	2	0	1	0	5	5	6
NAK	23-11-2020	Based on achievements of SKIN TN and other MA projects related to Short Food Supply Chain How to foster succesful adaptation of best practices, what are the challenges and possibilities.	webinar (interactive workshop)	41	1	0	0	2	0	33	5	0
NAK	16-12-2020	Key factors in scaling up agroforestry	webinar (interactive workshop)	76	1	0	0	2	0	58	15	0
IDELE	25-11-2020	cross exchange between EURAKNOS and EUROSHEEP TN	online workshop	13	2	0	0	2	0	9	0	0
USC (EFI collaboration)	15-10-2020	Exchange knowledge about agroforestry and climate change innovations in SouthWest of Europe	webinar	25	4	1	0	5	4	9	2	0
PSKW	08-12-2020	Exchange new insights in water desinfection possibilities and watertreatments for P. cryptogea based on the outcomes of the FERTINNOWA TN	webinar	17	3	0	0	2	0	2	10	0

Executing institution	CEV date	CEV purpose	Format (webinar/workshop)	Participants in total	Euraknos representatives	KIP representatives	SIB representatives	TN representatives	OG representatives	advisors/intermediaries	practitioners agriculture/forestry	other non-categorized
PSKW	10-12-2020	Exchange new insights in water disinfection possibilities and monitoring possibilities for <i>P. cryptogea</i> based on the outcomes of the FERTINNOWA TN	webinar	21	3	0	0	2	0	1	15	0
ARC	18-06-2020	Compare the ways of presenting information about innovative projects.	webinar	24	5	0	0	2	1	12	4	0
IFOAM EU	26-05-2020	TN project partners, practitioners, advisors and relevant topic-related EIP-AGRI Operation Groups to exchange the latest innovations and lessons learned in both research and trials as well as practical experiences of different farmers regarding new types of locally produced organic feed.	webinar	55	3	0	0	40	2	6	4	0

Networking activities with educational programmes and training initiatives have been less successful. Some partners e.g. RAU, USC and AUA are affiliated with universities. RAU (UK) carried out a workshop at the University of Cirencester where the EURAKNOS and EUREKA projects were presented for post-graduate agricultural students (event no. 53). In particular, the key outputs from WP 2 and 3 of EURAKNOS were presented. Also, RAU (UK) used the TN guide in the teaching programme to students (BSc in Food Environment and Society) in a designated module on the Theory and Practice of Knowledge Exchange.

Another activity related to students is the EURAKNOS Multi-Actor survey launched in July 2020 until December 2020 that had a total of 194 respondents including 13 students. The results showed that the students prefer to access knowledge in the form of text, video and presentations when searching online. Content-wise, the students prefer tutorials and innovative practices and to a lesser extent factsheets. Also, the survey focused on participating in projects and here students prefer to be part of projects based on their own ideas and to be involved in writing and to a lesser extent the expert panel, which would be expected. As the information was based on only 13 students, it is not possible to generalize.

When targeting education, primarily, partners provided a list with universities, some partners listed vocational schools and two partners listed a few advisor-training programmes. However, these lists were used with less success and the estimated number of participants was not reached. This may be related to partners having to do an extra effort to reach educational institutions. From these experiences, it is evident that the EUREKA project will profit very little from the EURAKNOS project in terms of contact and networking with educational institutions. It is relevant to link with educational curriculums, as this is where the knowledge sharing is taking place. At project planning, it must be taken into account that educational institutions and training are working with a much longer timeframe when planning compared to projects. It is important not to rely on that this will happen automatically because partners are affiliated with e.g. universities.

Regarding networking activities related to TNs and the networks of the TNs including OGs and other H2020 MAPS and networking activities with similar initiatives or organisations with a common interest at regional, national, European & international level, the EURAKNOS project has been successful as the vast majority of the estimated target numbers (number of events/activities) have been reached:

- Strengthening of the TN community through more than 28 bilateral meetings as well as 17 CEV's and 4 EURAKNOS workshops with TN participants;
- Exchange between TN players on best practices, methodologies, failures, gaps of TNs have been carried out mainly in WP2 and WP3 but also in discussions and email exchanges with TN players as well as through bilateral meetings;
- Awareness creation and engagement with all actors concerned (NGOs, farmers' organisations, SMEs, etc.) has been carried out by all partners at occasions where they encountered these actors. This included seven workshops focusing on the Explorer's Guide (report no. 39 and reports no 41-46)

- Enhancing the outreach of dissemination with end-users through EURAKNOS workshops and the Vision Paper.
- Validation of the project's results at the WG workshops: WP3 in Paris (report no. 22) and Budapest (report no. 10);
- Liaising with the EIP AGRI through participating in 3 EIP-AGRI seminars, other MAPs, as well as OGs and NRNs (report no. 15, 25, and 61);
- Collaboration with SCAR SWG AKIS: reaching out to policymakers through participating in 3 SCAR SWG AKIS meetings, one with a focused session about EURAKNOS (report no. 3, 17, 69);
- Exchange on experiences with international organisations such as FAO, GODAN, OECD etc. in terms of what is going on in the SIB, e.g. the development of the Vision Paper.

Originally, the CEVs were planned to take place as physical meetings with a duration of 2-3 days. At a CEV, invited guests from different countries meet and exchange ideas on topics of innovation in addition to visits to institutions, companies and businesses. Networking is indeed taking place at such events with intense interactions simply by spending time together (e.g. interacting during breaks and travelling). The COVID-19 pandemic had a huge influence on the ability of the EURAKNOS project to carry out the planned CEVs. Thus, the CEVs were converted to remote events with online meetings.

Due to the nature of online meetings, having to sit in front of the computer during the whole time of the event, it was not possible to maintain 2-3 days meetings. At this point in time, it was new to most of us to arrange and manoeuvre when conducting online meetings. We were working with how to create interactions between participants and leave room for networking at online meetings, e.g. find digital elements/programmes to be used to stimulate interaction. We also worked with various types of socializing, which may then lead to participants contacting each other, and also we made sure that everybody in the meeting got the possibility to introduce themselves and to speak their mind. Simple things such as starting the meeting a bit before and leaving time for small talk and socializing to take place is important and requires certain skills from the person leading the CEV. Partners were indeed innovative when stimulating interaction and networking. Thus, in addition to arranging the CEVs in itself, it was a considerable task to arrange how to promote interaction and networking between the participants when conducting online meetings.

Attending online meetings does not require travelling (easy and free of travelling costs), which is certainly an incentive for some to participate. On the other hand, meetings that requires on-site participation from specific people such as end-users may prove difficult to carry through to its full potential. Also, it will exclude persons that cannot use internet. The feedback from partners was that outreach was increased due to the meetings being held online compared to physical meetings (Table 5).

Seeing and hearing a person physically compared to seeing and hearing a person through a screen is definitely a barrier towards stimulating interaction and thus networking. It can be difficult to engage people at online meetings. Partners were accommodating this online 'fatigue' by conducting interactive sessions e.g. with Mural and to divide people into groups and use breakout rooms where all group members were involved in the conversation/discussion. Also, at online meetings, physical breaks are not possible to resemble, which is indeed the place where most networking is taking place. This was mitigated by making room/time for socializing during the meetings and also by making time for an online coffee break in front of the screen. Also, participants were encouraged at breaks to go outside, or to do some exercises and when returning to the online meeting this was the point of departure for socializing and starting the meeting.

The EURAKNOS project was extended into 2021 and will end in March 2021. In February, two big events were carried out with great success: 1. 'Raiders of the potentially lost Agricultural Knowledge' where the key outputs of the EURAKNOS project were presented in three individual sessions focusing on the Policy Brief, the Digital Platform, and the Thematic Networks Explorers Guide, 2. The final EURAKNOS conference with different sessions targeted at specific audiences in terms of how to make use of the EURAKNOS outputs and to make way for EUREKA with a focus on the end-user. Thus, both events focused on knowledge transfer from EURAKNOS to the sister project EUREKA.

The outreach of these two events as well as all the other networking activities is substantial as in total approximately 1800 persons participated/were reached. In terms of Networking activities related to TNs and the networks of the TNs including OGs and other H2020 MAPS, the estimated networking target was 100 participants and the reached number of participants was more than 750. Also, for networking activities with similar initiatives or organisations with a common interest at the regional, national, European & international level, the estimated networking target number (50 participants) was exceeded as more than 150 people were reached.

6. Conclusion

Networking outreach was successful with more than 1800 participants reached through 74 activities including 17 CEVs. In particular, networking activities related to TNs and the network of TNs as well as with similar initiatives or organizations with a common interest were successful, whereas the networking outreach related to educational institutions was rather limited. Creating awareness of the importance of reaching educational institutions is important and it is necessary to be proactive (early in the planning phase) in creating contacts. Being aware of the target audience is highly relevant and communication activities were tailored towards TNs and end-users and it would have been relevant also to include education and training in this context.

The COVID-19 pandemic created a situation where networking activities had to be carried out online and a few were cancelled. On one hand, this was challenging in terms of possibilities to perform networking as this is often very informal and something that happens during coffee breaks or in between meetings. On the other hand, this created a possibility to reach an increased number of participants, as more people were able to participate in an online event compared to having to travel (maybe even longer distances) to an event. This might be a valuable experience to carry further in the EURAKNOS project, as in the future, possibly more events and activities will be carried out through online meetings and workshops.

In order to get the full picture of the outreach and output of the EURAKNOS project, it is important to state the need for considering the Communication and Dissemination/Exploitation reports.

7. Next steps

EURAKNOS ends March 2021 and the experiences and findings will be utilized further in the EUREKA project (www.h2020eureka.eu/) where the focus is on the end-user. In EUREKA, a MA community-supported open source e-platform, the FarmBook, will be developed and the output from EURAKNOS will be transferred to the FarmBook, when this is functional. The contacts and networks gained in the EURAKNOS project will be utilized further in the EUREKA project. The EURAKNOS website will remain available and active 5 years after the project ends.

8. References

EURAKNOS (2020a): *The EURAKNOS Explorer's Guide to Thematic Networks*. Available at: <https://euraknos.fra1.digitaloceanspaces.com/production/deliverables/Explorers-guide-EN-interactive.pdf>

EURAKNOS (2020b): *Policy Brief*. Available at: <https://euraknos.fra1.digitaloceanspaces.com/production/deliverables/EURAKNOS-Policy-Brief.pdf>

EURAKNOS (2020c): *Vision paper: Developing High Impact: The Future EU-wide Open Source Knowledge Reservoir for Agriculture and Forestry*. Available at: https://euraknos.fra1.digitaloceanspaces.com/production/deliverables/EURAKNOS-Vision_Paper.pdf

EURAKNOS (2020d): *Networking Plan: Deliverable 5.3*.

Annex I - Deliverable 5.7 Networking activity reports

EURAKNOS

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

TASK 5.3

Deliverable Number	Work Package
5.7	WP5
Lead Beneficiary	Deliverable Author(S)
AU (ICROFS)	Malene Jakobsen Ilse Ankjær Rasmussen
Beneficiaries	Deliverable Co-Author (S)
AU (ICROFS), GLZ, IDELE, IfA, NAK, PSKW, RAU, UGent, USC	Laura Palczynski
Planned Delivery Date	Actual Delivery Date
31/03/2021	31/12/2021

Type of Deliverable	R	Document, report (excluding periodic and final reports)	X
	DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos	
	E	Ethics	

Dissemination Level	PU	Public	X
	CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

Annex I contains a list of the reports related to networking events. Each report is indicated by a number, which corresponds to the number indicated for each networking event presented in table 4, 5, and 6 in Deliverable D5.7. As networking activities can be of informal kind not every event comes with a full networking report. Also, for the networking reports where parts have not been filled in, these have been deleted to shorten up the Annex.

Networking event number 1

Exchange on best practices for Operational Groups between Poland and Flanders

Date: 28/1-2019

Location: Brussels, Belgium

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): Ugent, PSKW

Number of participants in total: 13

Type of networking event¹: Bilateral meeting

Highlights: Exchange on best practices for Operational Groups between Poland and Flanders

Networking event number 2

AGROLINK

Date: 6/6-2019

Location: Sint-Katelijne-Waver, Belgium

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): Ugent, PSKW

Number of participants in total: n.a.

Type of networking event¹: Bilateral meeting

Highlights: n.a.

Networking included the following participant types: n.a.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title) n.a.

Networking event number 3

SCAR AKIS MEETING

Date: 15/4-2019

Location: Dublin, Ireland

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): Ugent

Number of participants in total: n.a.

Type of networking event¹: Bilateral meeting

Highlights: n.a.

Networking included the following participant types: n.a.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title) n.a.

Networking event number 4

Hungarian AKIS working group meeting

Date: 5/7-2019

Location: Budapest, Hungary

Participants involved (names of organisations represented):
Euraknos partners of NAK: Tímea Reszkető and Enikő Fazekas

Number of participants in total: 82

Type of networking event¹: Workshop

Highlights:

There was a whole afternoon group of session during the meeting developing the Hungarian knowledge reservoir with external experts. In this session, we introduced EURAKNOS project and its processing to show how important a knowledge reservoir in the agri sector. We disseminated an infographic translated in Hungarian.

Networking included the following participant types:

n.a.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title)

n.a.

Networking event number 5

H2020-SC2 Coordinators' Day, REA

Date: 6 June 2019

Location: Brussels, Belgium

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): UGent

Number of participants in total: Almost 80 staff members of Coordinating Institutions

Type of networking event: bilateral meetings: H2020-SC2 Coordinators' Day, REA

Highlights: EURAKNOS was presented together with projects that deal with "food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime inland water research and the bioeconomy". The eight cluster sessions were followed by 2 thematic workshops and a general session focused on project life cycle.

Networking event number 6

3rd workshop on the role of H2020 Thematic Networks

Date: 11/6-2019

Location: Brussels, Belgium

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): UGent

Number of participants in total: n.a.

Type of networking event¹: Bilateral meeting: 3rd workshop on the role of H2020 Thematic Networks (in EU Agricultural Innovation). Organised by Copa Cogeca, TN leaders SWG SCAR AKIS, DG AGRI

Highlights: This 3rd workshop on TNs focusses on the question: how do these TNs learn from efforts? 10 TNs (including EURAKNOS) will show tangible examples where lessons learnt helped to increase impact. Furthermore, the newly accepted TN's 2019 will be introduced. The H2020 Multi-Actor project EURAKNOS showed how to explore synergies and enhance engagement among these TNs and other projects and they show how they work together.

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
x	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
x	Academic, University & Research		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
x	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Networking event number 7

North American Agroforestry Conference: Agroforestry for sustainable production + resilient landscapes

Date: 24-27 June 2019

Location: Corvallis, USA

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): University of Santiago de Compostela (USA)

Number of participants: 50

Types of participants: researchers, student, farmers, policy makers

Type of networking event¹: Bilateral meeting

Highlights: The Association for Temperate Agroforestry (AFTA) held its 16th biennial conference “Agroforestry for Sustainable Production + Resilient Landscapes” on June 24-27, 2019. The conference took place at Oregon State University in Corvallis, Oregon, USA and included oral and poster sessions and field trips to farms implementing agroforestry, mainly silvopasture, and other research sites, showing the advancement of agroforestry on the U.S. West Coast. In the AFTA conference, Dr Nuria Ferreiro-Domínguez from the University of Santiago de Compostela (USC) gave a presentation titled “Recommendations for policy makers in light of climate change: AFINET”. During this presentation the EURAKNOS project was presented to the audience.

Networking included:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
<input type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Government		
x	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title)

Nuria Ferreiro-Domínguez from the University of Santiago de Compostela (USC) during the AFTA conference.

Networking event number 8

Agro-innovation summit

Date: 26/6-2019

Location: Lisieux, France

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): UGent

Number of participants: 450

Types of participants: representatives from EIP-AGRI projects throughout Europe as well as local actors and experts.

Type of networking event¹: Bilateral meeting

Highlights: This event was the second European summit highlighting the potential of interactive innovation to address the challenges faced by European agriculture and forestry. EURAKNOS was presented to support the European Innovation Partnership for agricultural productivity and sustainability (EIP-AGRI) as a key tool for supporting interactive innovation in the sector both through local Operational Groups financed under the Common Agricultural Policy and transnational multi-actor research projects financed under the EU Research and Innovation policy (Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe).

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
X	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
X	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
x	Operational group		
	International organisations		
x	National Rural Networks		
	Innovation Networks		
x	Academic, University & Research		
x	Adviser/consultant/technician		
	Advisory association/company		
x	Chamber/council of agriculture		
	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
x	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
	Farmers association		
x	Government		
	Innovation broker		
	Media		
x	National Rural Networks		
	NGO		
	Other (please specify)		
x	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
	Umbrella organisation		
	Advisory training		
	Vocational training		
	Other (please specify)		

Networking event number 9

Coolbean 19: Soybeans, Stats, and the Big Picture.

Date: 19/7-2019

Location: Athens, Greece

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): n.a.

Number of participants: 20

Types of participants: university professors

Highlights: AUA participated in the specific event for the needs of delivering presentations about the organisation's involvement in research/project efforts. In this context, presentation of the EURAKNOS project took place. More specifically, AUA presented the EURAKNOS project (aim, objectives and progress), as well as some preliminary outcomes of preparatory work conducted for the needs of WP4. Meeting participants were very interested in getting to know what is the kind of work that is in progress in EURAKNOS. Particular interest was shown in the technical part of work in progress (i.e. design and development of the e-KRP).

Networking included:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
<input type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research	20	Attendees were university professors from the USA with expertise in soybean crops.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

 Networking event number 10

EURAKNOS Workshop

Date: 11-13/9-2019

Location: Budapest, Hungary

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): All EURAKNOS partners + KIP members

Number of participants in total: 27 + 32

Type of networking event¹³: Joint workshop – knowledge innovation panel

Highlights: During the parallel workshops, 20 recommendations were distilled.

Pictures:

¹³ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

Networking event number 12

National Rural Network, I2Connect

Date: 13/9/2019

Location: Budapest, Hungary

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): Elena Feo (Ugent) Elodie Pascal (GLZ), Philip Verbist (LFG) Eelke Wielinga (independent consultant)

Number of participants in total: 4

Type of networking event¹⁴: Bilateral meeting: GLZ met the WP4 leader of I2Connect (Eelke Wielinga) during the Budapest workshop (September 2019) in order to brainstorm on the involvement of OGs in the cross exchange visits

Highlights: Eelke Wielinga was invited to the Budapest Workshop of EURAKNOS and attended all sessions. The focus of our networking event was to discuss about possibilities of collaboration in a few cross-exchange visits of EURAKNOS in order to benefit from I2Connect and all previous work and expertise of Eelke Wielinga in past and current thematic networks.

Networking included the following participant types: n.a.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

¹⁴ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

Networking event number 13

EURAGRI meeting

Date: 23/9/2019

Location: Gent, Belgium

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): Ugent

Number of participants in total: n.a.

Type of networking event¹⁵: Bilateral meeting

Highlights: n.a.

Networking included the following participant types: n.a.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

¹⁵ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

 Networking event number 14

Inno4grass, bilateral meetings

Date: 15/10/2019

Location: Uppsala Sweden

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): all Inno4grass Partners +Elodie PASCAL (GLZ, EURAKNOS) all participants were partners of I4G and listed here on the homepage of I4G [Partners - Inno4Grass](#)

Number of participants in total: 18 +

Type of networking event¹⁶:

Networking + joint activities (reflection on sustainability of TNs). It was the final meeting of the project Inno4grass during which EURAKNOS has been presented.

Highlights: Short report of the networking event. Focus on the networking about EURAKNOS – presenting and or discussing about EURAKNOS. Do not report about the event itself if it is not related to EURAKNOS.

- Contacts established, promotion of EURAKNOS among Inno4Grass community for further collaboration

Networking included the following participant types: n.a.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title)

¹⁶ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

Networking event number 15

DG AGRI/EIP AGRI (Fabio Cossu)

Date: 16/10/2019

Location: n.a.

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): UGent, PSKW

Number of participants in total: 7

Type of networking event¹⁷: EIP-AGRI seminars

Highlights: Networking with with Fabio Cossu, contact at DG AGRI for the EIP-AGRI Service Point.

Networking included the following participant types: n.a.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

¹⁷ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

Networking event number 16

LIASON

Date: 19/11/2019

Location: Kaunas, Lithuania

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): n.a.

Number of participants in total: n.a.

Type of networking event¹⁸: Bilateral meeting

Highlights: n.a.

Networking included the following participant types: n.a.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

¹⁸ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

Networking event number 17

SWG AKIS

Date: 19/11-2019

Location: Kaunas, Lithuania

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): UGent, USC

Number of participants in total: SCAR SWG AKIS (number of participants?)

Type of networking event¹: SWG AKIS: We presented the EURAKNOS Results

Highlights: The SCAR SWG AKIS meeting in Kaunas. Discussion on measures take up during the current RD period: “Knowledge transfer and information actions” and “Advisory services, farm management and farm relief”. EURAKNOS results were presented in the framework of H2020 projects on knowledge exchange activities.

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
x	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
x	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
x	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
x	Academic, University & Research		
x	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
x	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
x	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
x	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
x x	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

 Networking event number 18

More with light (Meer met licht)

Date: 27th of November 2019

Location: PSKW, Sint-Katelijne-Waver (Belgium)

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): Redgrow bv, Kwekerij Vermeulen, ABZ Seeds, Inagro, Bayer Crop Science, Rijk Zwaan Breeding B.V., Vegobel, Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt, Herdi, Hoogstraten, Hortiplan, Nunhems / BasF, BASF Vegetable Seeds, Signify, Topkrop, Vyverberg, prayon, Dendauw Els bv, Solani, agriculteur, KBC, Den Boterhoek BVBA, Rijk Zwaan, Luminaid, Nunhems, Lycopersicon, Horticotrade nv, Sanac - Sint Katelijne Waver, Rijkzwaan bv, Vereijken Kwekerijen, Delphy Belgium cvba, Den Berk, Grodan, vanhissenhoven, Thomas More, Luc Beirinckx, PSKW, Aalst Fruit, Seasun, CVBA Heulens, Mols bvba, Agrolux, Tomerel, Adviesbureau Steur Vyverberg, Thomas More, Klasmann-Deilmann Belgium NV, Tuinbouwbedrijf Van Bulck BVBA, Maïs nv, Looije Agro Technics, Ugent, Stoffels bvba, Ludvig Svensson, UGent, Laboratorium voor Plantecologie, Primato, Les serres des hauts de France, Mechatronix, Vlaamse overheid, Tomaline bvba, Inagro, Bossaerts, Meer Fresh Products, PCH, BelOrta, Rijk Zwaan Belgium, Domarco, GEMAPA BVBA ,bvba TBMP, Hazera Seeds, Den Boschkant bvba, Starmeal nv, Proefcentrum Hoogstraten, VW Maxburg, Zuet BVBA, topack, Gonitrade, Green Production Systems bvba, Tuinbouwadvies Paul Baeyens, Oreon BV, Hydroponic, vakblad Groenten & Fruit, De Blackt, Neraco, Rijkzwaan, Axia Vegetable Seeds, Nunhems Netherlands Basf, PCG vzw, Laboratorium voor Plantecologie, Universiteit Gent, Producent 1299 Mortelmans Anne, Hortilux, Osram, GroentenNieuws, Den Horst BVBA, Den Berk Délice, Delphy, Improvement Centre, Bvba Van den Eynde, pijl Iv, Tuinderij Joosen, De Glastuin bvba, Oreon, Plantenkwekerij Van Engeland bvba, GAUTIER SEMENCES, Enza zaden

Number of participants: 2 EURAKNOS partners + 145 external attendees

Types of participants: primary producers, advisors, teachers, policy makers, SME's, technology providers

Type of networking event¹: Bilateral meeting

Highlights: During More With Light, PSKW and a series of project partners and companies active in the field of artificial light joint forces to present some of the most important project outcomes in the field of artificial light in the greenhouse crops. During a plenary session some key note speakers explained more general research outcomes while more practical and crop specific outcomes were explained in crop specific outbreak sessions. Sessions were dedicated to the fruit vegetables, leafy vegetables and strawberries. After the presentation sessions, attendees could join for a guided tour to the research facilities of the PSKW research center and visit the technology exposition.

During this exposition and networking event Ugent and PSKW interviewed attendees about their needs with regards to project communication and dissemination.

Networking included:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
<input type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
X	Academic, University & Research	9	
X	Adviser/consultant/technician	4	
X	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
X	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry	29	
X	Farmers & foresters, primary producers	65	
X	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
X	Innovation broker		
X	Media	3	
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
X	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)	21	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)	4	

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs Towards A European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

Figure 1: Impression of one of the guided tours along the cucumber trials with artificial light.

Figure 2: Impression of the networking event of More for Light

Figure 3: impression of the Euraknos survey and participants:

Networking event number 19

1st Conference of the young researchers in sustainable primary production and quality and food security

Date: 28-29 November 2019

Location: Lugo, Spain

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): University of Santiago de Compostela (USA)

Number of participants: 100

Types of participants: researchers, student, farmers

Highlights: The Strategic Research Group of the Campus Terra (University of Santiago de Compostela), BioReDes, held its 1st Conference of the young researchers in sustainable primary production and quality and food security on November 28-29, 2019. The conference took place at University of Santiago de Compostela in Lugo, Spain and included oral and poster sessions showing the research advancement in the primary sector within the University of the Santiago de Compostela. In the BioReDes conference, Dario Arias-Martínez from the University of Santiago de Compostela (USC) gave a presentation titled “European Agricultural Sector Innovation”. During this presentation some results of the WP2 (Compile and evaluate EIP-AGRI KR (TNs) outputs) of the EURAKNOS project were presented to the audience.

Networking included:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
<input type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title):

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs Towards A European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

Dario Arias-Martínez from the University of Santiago de Compostela (USC) during the BioReDes conference.

Networking event number 20

DISARM Consortium Meeting

Date: 3-4th December 2019

Location: Brussels, Belgium

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): DISARM partners: ILVO, Ghent University, COPA-COGECA, International Dairy Federation, Nutrition Sciences, SEGES, ZLTO, Wageningen University & Research, ACTA, IDELE, ITAVI, IFIP, Anprogapor, IfA, AUA. USAMV, Angst, LLU

Number of participants: Approx 30

Types of participants:

TN partners

Highlights: EURAKNOS mentioned in coffee breaks

Networking included:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
<input type="checkbox"/> Y	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/> Y	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/> Y	Academic, University & Research		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organization		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

Networking event number 21

UN Climate Conference: COP25

Date: 3-4 December 2019

Location: Madrid, Spain

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): University of Santiago de Compostela (USA)

Number of participants: 70

Types of participants: Researchers, farmers (World farmer association), NGOs, representatives of the Global Alliance for Climate Smart Agriculture and Global Research Alliance, policy makers, representatives of international Universities

Highlights: The UN Climate Conference: COP25 took place in Madrid, Spain on December 2019. UN Climate Conference brought together governments, businesses, local authorities and civil society in Madrid to express support for the Paris Agreement and for urgent climate action. During the UN Climate Conference María Rosa Mosquera-Losada from the University of Santiago de Compostela (USC) gave a presentation about innovation and policy in which the EURAKNOS project was presented.

Networking included:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		Global Alliance for Climate Smart Agriculture and Global Research Alliance
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		World farmer association
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Government		
	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

María Rosa Mosquera-Losada from the University of Santiago de Compostela (USC) during the UN Climate Conference: COP25

Networking event number 22

EURAKNOS Paris workshop

Date: 11-13/12-2019

Location: Paris, France

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): [list of participants](#)

Number of participants: 24 from EURAKNOS consortium + 36 external participants

Types of participants: primary producers (farmers), advisors, teachers, researchers, policy makers, TN's stakeholders (coordinators or partners)

Highlights:

It was a one day and a half workshop meeting together different kind of end-users and stakeholders of TNs. Participants were invited to join one of the 4 Working Group, working in parallel. Contributions from participants were useful to identify and file recommendations for best methodologies and practices:

- 1) to select, collect and store in a harmonized way in a HIKR
- 2) to design a HIKR
- 3) to disseminate, communicate to and inform end-users
- 4) for MA involvement during the different stages of TNs

It was a first important step for the EURAKNOS WP3.

Networking included:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
✓	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)	36	
✓	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
✓	Operational group		
✓	National Rural Networks		
✓	Innovation Networks		
✓	Academic, University & Research		
✓	Adviser/consultant/technician		
✓	Advisory association/company		
✓	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
✓	Farmers association		
✓	Government		
✓	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
✓	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
✓	Umbrella organisation		

Participants to the EURAKNOS Paris workshop

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Plenary introduction workshop meeting

2 examples of the 4 working group, working in parallel

Networking event number 23

Information day to advisors 1/2020

Date: 14.01.2020

Location: Pärnu, Estonia

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): Rural Development Foundation, Private limited company Maritell ATV, Agricultural Research Center, EIP-AGRI Service Point, Pärnumaa Talupidajate Nõuandekeskus OÜ, Ida-Virumaa Farmers' Union, Saaremaa Advisory Center, TFTAK, OÜ Luksagry, Organic Farming Cooperation Council, Ministry of Rural Affairs

Number of participants: 34

Types of participants: (primary producers, advisors, teachers, students, policy makers, SME's etc): advisors, policy makers, researchers, rural developers.

Highlights: Full information day is officially uploaded on ARC webpage and available on Youtube <https://maainfo.ee/index.php?id=6958&page=3394&>

Networking included:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks	34	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		

Study day: WaterWijs

Date: 21 January 2020

Location: PSKW, Sint-Katelijne-Waver (Belgium)

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): Aquafin NV, Gemeente Kontich, Proefcentrum Hoogstraten, Power Plastics bv, Proefstation voor de groenteteelt, Bertels bvba, Vlaams Kenniscentrum Water (Vlakwa/VITO), Bakker Belgium Nv, Microflor NV, PCH, Belgische plantenkwekerij, Crotoni bvba, Vlaamse Landmaatschappij, Prominent, Hortispeed BV, Provincie Antwerpen, PCS, HACH – Mechelen, Saint-Gobain, Cultilene, Codema systems group, ICL, AQUA D&S, Verhoeve Milieu en Water, CropDesign NV, Goris-Verlinden, CATEC, Agrozone, Pidpa, Vlaamse Overheid - dept. Landbouw & Visserij, Ets. Arm. Op de Beeck BVBA, Maritech GCV, prayon, Primato, bvba TBMP, Aquafin, Stoffels, Hortiplan, Bvba mave, Bodemkundige Dienst van België, Boerenbond, Den Boschkant, Hazera Seeds, Lycopersicon, PCG, Verbruggen Agro te Leest, POM Antwerpen, CropDesign n.v. – BASF, Hortiplan NV, Inagro, KUL, MJ tech, JVR Tecmar, Bodemkundige dienst België, Ridder, BelOrta, KULeuven, Van Dessel automatisatie

Number of participants: 2 from EURAKNOS consortium + 80 external participants

Types of participants: primary producers (farmers), advisors, researchers, policy makers, Industry,

Highlights: On the 21st of January PSKW organized a study day focusing on water related topics. For this event the targeted audience group were growers and researchers. The study day started with a farm demo visit at a MBBR-filtration (Moving Bed Biofilm Reactor) near the research station, where attendees were able to see the functions and the target of this filtration unit. After the field visit, the attendees followed several presentations with a strong focus on drought and flooding in Flanders together with some potential solutions which are being tested in different projects where PSKW is involved in. After this short introduction of different projects and solutions, the attendees had the opportunity to gather more in-depth information of the different projects and solutions that have been explained during the presentations. Finally a guided tour through the research station was organized wherein everyone was being informed about the different tests that were being carried out and how PSKW is committed to water management. At the end of the tour there was an opportunity to network with other partners or with technology suppliers at the technology fair. This was the ideal time for Euraknos to highlight and network with the attendees by conducting a survey about their needs for communication and dissemination. The survey was individually conducted between a partner of EURAKNOS and an attendee by filling in the questions on a tablet.

Networking included:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
✓	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)	82	
	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
	Operational group		
	National Rural Networks		
	Innovation Networks		
✓	Academic, University & Research		
✓	Adviser/consultant/technician		
✓	Advisory association/company		
✓	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
	Farmers association		
	Government		
	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
✓	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
	Umbrella organisation		

Attendees visiting a demo at a farmer's field

Presentation on drought and flooding in Flanders

Attendees visiting the different water related projects of PSKW

Visit at the technology fair

Networking event number 25

EIP-AGRI seminar: “New Skills for Digital Farming”.

Date: 05-06/2-2020

Location: Aranjuez, Madrid, Spain

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): n.a.

Number of participants: 20

Types of participants: Advisors, contractors, representatives of universities and research organizations, farmer/forester representatives, policy makers, representatives of H2020 projects.

Highlights: There was a time slot specifically dedicated to presentation of H2020 projects and other relevant initiatives. Presentation of each project/effort had to take place in the form of a pitch. The allocated time frame was four (4) minutes. Presentation of EURAKNOS focused on general aspects of work in progress with a specific focus on the design and development part. The audience showed interest in our effort and a number of positive comments were provided as feedback.

Networking included:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		OECD representatives
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

There is no evidence with regard to number of participants per each of the above selected attendee categories. Total number of participants: ~100.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): Sylvia Bursens has taken some pictures of the delivery of the presentation.

Networking event number 26

Introduction to EURAKNOS

Date: 11th February

Location: Royal Agricultural University, Cirencester, UK

Participants involved: Agricultural students.

Number of participants: 10

Types of participants: Students

Highlights: An overview of the EURAKNOS project was presented including aims and objectives and how students can access valuable ready for practice outcomes from thematic networks. An end user journey exercise was completed to find out where the students go for knowledge exchange and their preferences for information was sort as end users of knowledge ready for practice.

Networking included: Innovation broker

Pictures: n.a.

Networking event number 27

EUFRAS Annual Assembly Meeting.

Date: 25/2-2020

Location: Athens, Greece

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): (a complete list of participating organisations is not available; yet there was representation of TEAGASC, EUFRAS, as well as the i2Connect, Best4Soil, IPM and FAIRShare projects).

Number of participants: 50

Types of participants: Advisors, H2020 project representatives

Highlights: EURAKNOS was presented during the annual assembly meeting of EUFRAS. The presentation took place in a specific time slot dedicated to presentations of H2020 projects (i2connect, Best4Soil, IPM and FAIRShare projects were also presented). The presentation that was delivered offered an overview of work in progress in the context of EURAKNOS. It was also mentioned that this was a great opportunity to present our work given that advisors are a core target group. There was increased interest in our work. The coordinating team of the i2connect project expressed the intention to establish a communication channel. They also have an interest in getting informed about the technologies to be adopted in EURAKNOS for the needs of the e-KRP development. There were also discussions with a representative of the coordinating team of the Best4Soil TN. There has been expression of interest in collaborating with us and providing data to be stored into the EURAKNOS repository.

Networking included:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

There is no evidence with regard to number of participants per each of the above selected attendee categories. Total number of participants: ~50.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

Networking event number 28

Smartprotect

Date: 3/3-2020

Location: n.a.

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): Ugent

Number of participants: n.a.

Types of participants: n.a.

Type of event: Bilateral meeting

Highlights: n.a.

Networking included: n.a.

Pictures: n.a.

Networking event number 29 – POSTPONED DUE TO COVID19

SCAR SWG AKIS on Social innovation

Date: 19-20/3-2020

Location: Budapest, Hungary

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): Ugent

Number of participants: n.a.

Types of participants: n.a.

Type of event: SWG AKIS

Highlights: n.a.

Networking included: n.a.

Pictures: n.a.

Networking event number 30, 31

IfA networking activities

Date: 23, 24 March 2020

Location: Online (UK, Ireland)

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): IfA, AHDB, STAMP consortium

Number of participants: 5, 17

Types of participants:

Agricultural levy board (UK), researchers, advisors

Highlights: EURAKNOS mentioned during introductions

Networking included:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
<input type="checkbox"/> Y	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/> Y	Academic, University & Research		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input type="checkbox"/> Y	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/> Y	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organization		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

Networking event number 32 – POSTPONED DUE TO COVID19

AKIS conference

Date: 26-27/3-2020

Location: Zagreb, Croatia

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): Ugent, RAU

Number of participants: n.a.

Types of participants: n.a.

Type of event: Bilateral meeting

Highlights: n.a.

Networking included: n.a.

Pictures: n.a.

Networking event number 33

Talk with agricultural advisors

Date: 15/4/2020

Location: online/mail Germany

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): n.a.

Number of participants in total: 5 external in total

Type of networking event¹⁹: Bilateral meeting

Highlights: n.a.

¹⁹ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
<input type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research		
X	Adviser/consultant/technician	5	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

Networking event number 34

SWAMPS meeting

Date: 22/4/2020

Location: GLZ, Germany

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): n.a.

Number of participants in total: 2 (one EURAKNOS partner and one external partner)

Type of networking event²⁰: Bilateral meeting (SVAMPS)

Highlights: Presentation of task progress

Networking included the following participant types: n.a.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

²⁰ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

Networking event number 35 - POSTPONED DUE TO COVID19

EIP-AGRI Seminar CAP Strategic Plans and key role of AKIS Member States

Date: 22/4- 2020

Location: Warsaw, Poland

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): UGent

Number of participants: n.a.

Types of participants: n.a.

Highlights: n.a.

Networking event number 38 - CANCELLED DUE TO COVID19

Copa-Cogeca 'H2020 Thematic Networks (TNs) in Agricultural Innovation'

Date: 11/5- 2020

Location: Brussels, Belgium

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): UGent

Number of participants: n.a.

Types of participants: n.a.

Highlights: n.a.

EURAKNOS

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System Online workshop 1

Date: 11/5-2020. 10:30-12:00

Location: webinar hosted by ICROFS

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): The following partners presented below, participated in one or several of seven webinars under the same heading: EURAKNOS consortium, Pilze-Nagy Kft., PROUNION, Estonian Organic Farming Foundation, BIOFRUITNET, 4Science, Wageningen University, Estonian Agricultural Registers and Information Board, Eurocommerce, Animal Health Europe, Terra humana, NETWERKENCO, Animal Health Europe, Fundatia ADEPT Transilvania, AHDB/Farmer, university of Kassel, Interbev, Eurogroup for Animals, PANACEA, INNOSETA, WINETWORK, Disarm, French institute of Vine, European Environmental Bureau, University of Foggia, Seges, CERERE, Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Service, Unacoma, best4soil, FIBL, INCREDIBLE, Insitute of Technology at Tralee, SAI Platform, IDELE, Ireland's Seafood Development Agency, Teagasc (H2020: FAIRshare), NETWERKENCO, ROSEWOOD4.0, Agroknow, Agricultural University of Athens, Bioforum Vlaanderen, Estonian Advisory Service, Innovisa, VLK+EUFRRAS, Greenpeace, UNITO, ITAB, AGRA, Aarhus University, SLU, National Unit for EIP – French ministry for agriculture and food, Costello group, EuroSheep, Wageningen University, THE EUROPEAN COUNCIL OF YOUNG FARMERS, Alexandro Stulginskio University, EuroDairy, Suwanu, Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Service, Regenerative Farming Mentor, Eurocoop, Foundation for Organic Agriculture - BIOSELENA, SMARTPROTECT, University of Hohenheim, Kingshay, Institute for Agrostrategies and Innovation, Organic research center, PROMETER farmers association, Croatian Chamber of Agriculture, KU Leuven, Agridea, The Chamber of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania, Maastricht University, University of Polvdiv, Hungarian NRN, Young farmer's Association, Steinbeis-Europa-Zentrum.

Number of participants: 51

Types of participants: Primary producers, advisors, consultants, policy makers, researchers,

Highlights:

- Guide to enter the online meeting
- Prerequisite for the upcoming workshops
- Introduction to the "EURAKNOS Explorers guide"
- Introduction to the methodology of the workshops.
- Explanation of how to choose between the six workshops/webinars held the following week.
- An overview of the guide on how to prepare and run a Thematic Network (TN)

Networking included:

It is not possible to state how many attendees within the individual seven workshops

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
X	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
X	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
X	Academic, University & Research		
X	Adviser/consultant/technician		
X	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
X	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
X	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
X	Farmers association		
X	Government		
X	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
X	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
X	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
X	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
X	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

Networking event number 40

Date: 12/5/2020

Location: GLZ, Germany

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): GLZ, Bröös, Nefertiti TN:

Number of participants in total: 6 in total (one EURAKNOS partner and 5 external partners)

Type of networking event²¹: Bilateral meeting: Nefertiti / Euraknos Cross visit

Highlights: Short report of the networking event. Focus on the networking about EURAKNOS – presenting and or discussing about EURAKNOS. Do not report about the event itself if it is not related to EURAKNOS. CEV preparations.

Networking included the following participant types: n.a.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title). n.a.

²¹ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

EURAKNOS

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

Online workshop 3

Date: 18th May 2020, 10:00-11:00

Location: online webinar hosted by ICROFS

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): The following partners presented below, participated in one or several of seven webinars under the same heading:

EURAKNOS consortium, Pilze-Nagy Kft., PROUNION, Estonian Organic Farming Foundation, BIOFRUITNET, 4Science, Wageningen University, Estonian Agricultural Registers and Information Board, Eurocommerce, Animal Health Europe, Terra humana, NETWERKENCO, Animal Health Europe, Fundatia ADEPT Transilvania, AHDB/Farmer, university of Kassel, Interbev, Eurogroup for Animals, PANACEA, INNOSETA, WINETWORK, Disarm, French institute of Vine, European Environmental Bureau, University of Foggia, Seges, CERERE, Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Service, Unacoma, best4soil, FIBL, INCREDIBLE, Insitute of Technology at Tralee, SAI Platform, IDELE, Ireland's Seafood Development Agency, Teagasc (H2020: FAIRshare), NETWERKENCO, ROSEWOOD4.0, Agroknow, Agricultural University of Athens, Bioforum Vlaanderen, Estonian Advisory Service, Innovisa, VLK+EUFRRAS, Greenpeace, UNITO, ITAB, AGRA, Aarhus University, SLU, National Unit for EIP – French ministry for agriculture and food, Costello group, EuroSheep, Wageningen University, THE EUROPEAN COUNCIL OF YOUNG FARMERS, Alexandro Stulginskio University, EuroDairy, Suwanu, Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Service, Regenerative Farming Mentor, Eurocoop, Foundation for Organic Agriculture - BIOSELENA, SMARTPROTECT, University of Hohenheim, Kingshay, Institute for Agrostrategies and Innovation, Organic research center, PROMETER farmers association, Croatian Chamber of Agriculture, KU Leuven, Agridea, The Chamber of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania, Maastricht University, University of Polvdiv, Hungarian NRN, Young farmer's Association, Steinbeis-Europa-Zentrum.

Number of participants: 40

Types of participants: Advisors, consultants, policy makers, researchers.

Highlights:

- The roles of different actors in the Multi Actor Approach in Thematic Networks
- Who, When, How different actors are valuable to a TN

It was not possible to state how many attendees within the individual seven workshops

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
X	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
x	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
x	Academic, University & Research		
x	Adviser/consultant/technician		
x	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
x	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
x	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
x	Farmers association		
x	Government		
X	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
x	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
x	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
x	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
x	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

Networking event number 42

EURAKNOS

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System Online workshop 3

Date: 18th May 2020, 14:00-15:00

Location: webinar hosted by ICROFS

Participants involved (names of organizations represented): The following partners presented below, participated in one or several of seven webinars under the same heading:

EURAKNOS consortium, Pilze-Nagy Kft., PROUNION, Estonian Organic Farming Foundation, BIOFRUITNET, 4Science, Wageningen University, Estonian Agricultural Registers and Information Board, Eurocommerce, Animal Health Europe, Terra humana, NETWERKENCO, Animal Health Europe, Fundatia ADEPT Transilvania, AHDB/Farmer, university of Kassel, Interbev, Eurogroup for Animals, PANACEA, INNOSETA, WINETWORK, Disarm, French institute of Vine, European Environmental Bureau, University of Foggia, Seges, CERERE, Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Service, Unacoma, best4soil, FIBL, INCREDIBLE, Insitute of Technology at Tralee, SAI Platform, IDELE, Ireland's Seafood Development Agency, Teagasc (H2020: FAIRshare), NETWERKENCO, ROSEWOOD4.0, Agroknow, Agricultural University of Athens, Bioforum Vlaanderen, Estonian Advisory Service, Innovisa, VLK+EUFAS, Greenpeace, UNITO, ITAB, AGRA, Aarhus University, SLU, National Unit for EIP – French ministry for agriculture and food, Costello group, EuroSheep, Wageningen University, THE EUROPEAN COUNCIL OF YOUNG FARMERS, Alexandro Stulginskio University, EuroDairy, Suwanu, Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Service, Regenerative Farming Mentor, Eurocoop, Foundation for Organic Agriculture - BIOSELENA, SMARTPROTECT, University of Hohenheim, Kingshay, Institute for Agrostrategies and Innovation, Organic research center, PROMETER farmers association, Croatian Chamber of Agriculture, KU Leuven, Agridea, The Chamber of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania, Maastricht University, University of Polvdiv, Hungarian NRN, Young farmer's Association, Steinbeis-Europa-Zentrum.

Number of participants: 36

Types of participants: advisors, consultants, policy makers, researchers, Small and middle size entrepreneurs

Highlights:

- Assessing end-user needs and identifying the best ways to harvest and co-generate user-friendly knowledge
- Influence the EURAKNOS Explorers Guide regarding end-user needs
- Feedback to integrate in the guidelines for the future TNs

Networking included:

It is not possible to state how many attendees within the individual seven workshops

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
x	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
x	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
x	Academic, University & Research		
x	Adviser/consultant/technician		
x	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
x	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
x	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
x	Farmers association		
x	Government		
x	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
x	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
x	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
x	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
x	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

Networking event number 43

EURAKNOS

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

Online workshop 4

Date: 19th May 2020, 10:00-11:00

Location: webinar hosted by ICROFS

Participants involved (names of organizations represented): The following partners presented below, participated in one or several of seven webinars under the same heading:

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System: EURAKNOS consortium, Pilze-Nagy Kft., PROUNION, Estonian Organic Farming Foundation, BIOFRUITNET, 4Science, Wageningen University, Estonian Agricultural Registers and Information Board, Eurocommerce, Animal Health Europe, Terra humana, NETWERKENCO, Animal Health Europe, Fundatia ADEPT Transilvania, AHDB/Farmer, university of Kassel, Interbev, Eurogroup for Animals, PANACEA, INNOSETA, WINETWORK, Disarm, French institute of Vine, European Environmental Bureau, University of Foggia, Seges, CERERE, Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Service, Unacoma, best4soil, FIBL, INCREDIBLE, Insitute of Technology at Tralee, SAI Platform, IDELE, Ireland's Seafood Development Agency, Teagasc (H2020: FAIRshare), NETWERKENCO, ROSEWOOD4.0, Agroknow, Agricultural University of Athens, Bioforum Vlaanderen, Estonian Advisory Service, Innovisa, VLK+EUFAS, Greenpeace, UNITO, ITAB, AGRA, Aarhus University, SLU, National Unit for EIP – French ministry for agriculture and food, Costello group, EuroSheep, Wageningen University, THE EUROPEAN COUNCIL OF YOUNG FARMERS, Alexandro Stulginskio University, EuroDairy, Suwanu, Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Service, Regenerative Farming Mentor, Eurocoop, Foundation for Organic Agriculture - BIOELENA, SMARTPROTECT, University of Hohenheim, Kingshay, Institute for Agrostrategies and Innovation, Organic research center, PROMETER farmers association, Croatian Chamber of Agriculture, KU Leuven, Agridea, The Chamber of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania, Maastricht University, University of Polvdiv, Hungarian NRN, Young farmer's Association, Steinbeis-Europa-Zentrum.

Number of participants: 38

Types of participants: advisors, consultants, policy makers, researchers

Highlights:

- Designing your end-user engagement strategy
- How to validate the dissemination and exploitation pathways

Networking included:

It is not possible to state how many attendees within the individual seven workshops

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
X	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
X	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
X	Academic, University & Research		
X	Adviser/consultant/technician		
X	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
X	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
X	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
X	Farmers association		
X	Government		
X	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
X	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
X	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
X	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
X	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

Networking event number 44

EURAKNOS

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System Online workshop 5

Date: 19th May 2020, 14:00-15:00

Location: webinar hosted by ICROFS

Participants involved (names of organizations represented): The following partners presented below, participated in one or several of seven webinars under the same heading:

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

EURAKNOS consortium, Pilze-Nagy Kft., PROUNION, Estonian Organic Farming Foundation, BIOFRUITNET, 4Science, Wageningen University, Estonian Agricultural Registers and Information Board, Eurocommerce, Animal Health Europe, Terra humana, NETWERKENCO, Animal Health Europe, Fundatia ADEPT Transilvania, AHDB/Farmer, university of Kassel, Interbev, Eurogroup for Animals, PANACEA, INNOSETA, WINETWORK, Disarm, French institute of Vine, European Environmental Bureau, University of Foggia, Seges, CERERE, Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Service, Unacoma, best4soil, FIBL, INCREDIBLE, Insitute of Technology at Tralee, SAI Platform, IDELE, Ireland's Seafood Development Agency, Teagasc (H2020: FAIRshare), NETWERKENCO, ROSEWOOD4.0, Agroknow, Agricultural University of Athens, Bioforum Vlaanderen, Estonian Advisory Service, Innovisa, VLK+EUFRRAS, Greenpeace, UNITO, ITAB, AGRA, Aarhus University, SLU, National Unit for EIP – French ministry for agriculture and food, Costello group, EuroSheep, Wageningen University, THE EUROPEAN COUNCIL OF YOUNG FARMERS, Alexandro Stulginskio University, EuroDairy, Suwanu, Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Service, Regenerative Farming Mentor, Eurocoop, Foundation for Organic Agriculture - BIOSELENA, SMARTPROTECT, University of Hohenheim, Kingshay, Institute for Agrostrategies and Innovation, Organic research center, PROMETER farmers association, Croatian Chamber of Agriculture, KU Leuven, Agridea, The Chamber of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania, Maastricht University, University of Polvdiv, Hungarian NRN, Young farmer's Association, Steinbeis-Europa-Zentrum.

Number of participants: 34

Types of participants: advisors, consultants, policy makers, researchers,

Highlights:

- Improving the common format of practice abstract
- Insight into different ways to dissemina

Networking included:

It is not possible to state how many attendees within the individual seven workshops

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
x	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
x	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
x	Academic, University & Research		
x	Adviser/consultant/technician		
x	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
x	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
x	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
x	Farmers association		
x	Government		
x	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
x	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
x	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
x	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
x	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

EURAKNOS

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

Online workshop 6

Date: 20th May 2020, 10:00-11:30

Location: webinar hosted by ICROFS

Participants involved (names of organizations represented):

The following partners presented below, participated in one or several of seven webinars under the same heading:

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

EURAKNOS consortium, Pilze-Nagy Kft., PROUNION, Estonian Organic Farming Foundation, BIOFRUITNET, 4Science, Wageningen University, Estonian Agricultural Registers and Information Board, Eurocommerce, Animal Health Europe, Terra humana, NETWERKENCO, Animal Health Europe, Fundatia ADEPT Transilvania, AHDB/Farmer, university of Kassel, Interbev, Eurogroup for Animals, PANACEA, INNOSETA, WINETWORK, Disarm, French institute of Vine, European Environmental Bureau, University of Foggia, Seges, CERERE, Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Service, Unacoma, best4soil, FIBL, INCREDIBLE, Insitute of Technology at Tralee, SAI Platform, IDELE, Ireland's Seafood Development Agency, Teagasc (H2020: FAIRshare), NETWERKENCO, ROSEWOOD4.0, Agroknow, Agricultural University of Athens, Bioforum Vlaanderen, Estonian Advisory Service, Innovisa, VLK+EUFRAS, Greenpeace, UNITO, ITAB, AGRA, Aarhus University, SLU, National Unit for EIP – French ministry for agriculture and food, Costello group, EuroSheep, Wageningen University, THE EUROPEAN COUNCIL OF YOUNG FARMERS, Alexandro Stulginskio University, EuroDairy, Suwanu, Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Service, Regenerative Farming Mentor, Eurocoop, Foundation for Organic Agriculture - BIOSELENA, SMARTPROTECT, University of Hohenheim, Kingshay, Institute for Agrostrategies and Innovation, Organic research center, PROMETER farmers association, Croatian Chamber of Agriculture, KU Leuven, Agridea, The Chamber of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania, Maastricht University, University of Polvdiv, Hungarian NRN, Young farmer's Association, Steinbeis-Europa-Zentrum.

Number of participants: 31

Types of participants: advisors, it, policy makers, researchers, Small and middle size entrepreneurs.

Highlights:

- Design and strategy of the future database and how TNs can present themselves on the digital platform
- Influence the EURAKNOS Explorers Guide regarding future database
- Input on how TNs want to present themselves on the platform.

Networking included:

It is not possible to state how many attendees within the individual seven workshops

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
X	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
X	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
X	Academic, University & Research		
X	Adviser/consultant/technician		
X	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
X	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
X	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
X	Farmers association		
X	Government		
X	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
X	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
X	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
X	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
X	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

EURAKNOS

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System Online workshop 7

Date: 20th May 2020, 14:00-15:00

Location: webinar hosted by ICROFS

Participants involved (names of organizations represented):

The following partners presented below, participated in one or several of seven webinars under the same heading:

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

EURAKNOS consortium, Pilze-Nagy Kft., PROUNION, Estonian Organic Farming Foundation, BIOFRUITNET, 4Science, Wageningen University, Estonian Agricultural Registers and Information Board, Eurocommerce, Animal Health Europe, Terra humana, NETWERKENCO, Animal Health Europe, Fundatia ADEPT Transilvania, AHDB/Farmer, university of Kassel, Interbev, Eurogroup for Animals, PANACEA, INNOSETA, WINETWORK, Disarm, French institute of Vine, European Environmental Bureau, University of Foggia, Seges, CERERE, Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Service, Unacoma, best4soil, FIBL, INCREDIBLE, Insitute of Technology at Tralee, SAI Platform, IDELE, Ireland's Seafood Development Agency, Teagasc (H2020: FAIRshare), NETWERKENCO, ROSEWOOD4.0, Agroknow, Agricultural University of Athens, Bioforum Vlaanderen, Estonian Advisory Service, Innovisa, VLK+EUFRRAS, Greenpeace, UNITO, ITAB, AGRA, Aarhus University, SLU, National Unit for EIP – French ministry for agriculture and food, Costello group, EuroSheep, Wageningen University, THE EUROPEAN COUNCIL OF YOUNG FARMERS, Alexandro Stulginskio University, EuroDairy, Suwanu, Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Service, Regenerative Farming Mentor, Eurocoop, Foundation for Organic Agriculture - BIOSELENA, SMARTPROTECT, University of Hohenheim, Kingshay, Institute for Agrostrategies and Innovation, Organic research center, PROMETER farmers association, Croatian Chamber of Agriculture, KU Leuven, Agridea, The Chamber of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania, Maastricht University, University of Polvdiv, Hungarian NRN, Young farmer's Association, Steinbeis-Europa-Zentrum.

Number of participants: 34

Types of participants: advisors, consultants, policy makers, researchers, Small and middle size entrepreneurs.

Highlights:

- Increasing impact and sustainability
- How to choose and when to use what kind of indicators

Networking included: It is not possible to state how many attendees within the individual seven workshops

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
x	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
x	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
x	Academic, University & Research		
x	Adviser/consultant/technician		
x	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
x	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
x	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
x	Farmers association		
x	Government		
x	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
x	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
x	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
x	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
x	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

Networking event number 47

Digital cross-exchange “Web-based exchange of practical farming knowledge to support and inspire agricultural innovation”

Date: 26/5-2020

Location: Online

Participants involved: Representatives of IFOAM Organics Europe, ICROFS, ORC, SLU, FiBL, Soil Association, ITAB, FNAB, Demeter, Bioland, Naturland Beratung, Prograin Organic, Estonian Organic Farming Foundation, Prodabio, ILVO Vlaanderen, Innovatiesteunpunt, AIAB, Danube Soya Serbia, Ecovalia, OF&G, Ausumgård, Bio Nouvelle-Aquitaine, Bio en Grand Est, Seges, UFAB Bio, CAAE, Nutreco, Bioschwein Austria, Varkensloket, Universidad de Córdoba, National Chung Hsing University, Universitat de Lleida, German Jordanian University, Universiteti i Prishtinës, Top Æg ApS, The Rural Economy and Agricultural Societies, Chambres d'Agriculture de Bretagne & Pays de la Loire, Junta de Andalucía, organic pig farmer & other end users

Number of participants: 76

Types of participants: EURAKNOS partners, TN OK-Net EcoFeed project partners and Innovation Group members, end users: advisors dealing with the topic, farmers and farmers' associations, researchers/scientists

Highlights: The online event (originally planned to be held in Billund, Denmark, and to include field trips to various farms) brought together TN project partners, practitioners, advisors as well as relevant topic-related EIP-AGRI Operation Groups to exchange about the latest innovations and lessons learned in both research and trials performed as well as practical experiences of different farmers regarding new types of locally produced organic feed (with a focus on green protein for pigs and poultry, e.g. clover grass). The live presentations and videos were followed by a discussion in which participants could directly address the speakers, comment, and ask questions via the chat and share their views and experiences. The webinar ended with a presentation of the online platform [Organic Farm Knowledge](#), a joint venture of OK-Nets Arable and EcoFeed. To evaluate the online meeting and identify potential for improvement, oral feedback was collected during OK-Net EcoFeed project meeting on 27 May, asking the participants for their impression at the start of the meeting. While most were very satisfied with the CEV (e.g. good organisation, interesting presentations, well-constructed discussion), several aspects to consider were highlighted, such as the language barrier (no translation options), technical problems at the start as well as the timing (some participants felt there was not enough time for presentations and/or discussion, or that they were waiting too long before the actual start). Additionally, a follow-up survey was conducted to collect feedback on how to best organise online meetings with farmers and engage and reach end users (completed by 11 respondents from different European countries), revealing that the email invitation was the most common way participants got to know about the digital cross-exchange.

Networking included: (Please note that in the case of some organisations, several types apply!)

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
x	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)	At least 17	OK-Net EcoFeed
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
x	Operational group	At least 3	BioBIG, 4AGEPROD, PROGRAILIVE
x	International organisations	At least 17	FOAM Organics Europe, ICROFS
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
x	Innovation Networks		11 Innovation Groups of TN OK-Net EcoFeed
x	Academic, University & Research	At least 9	AU, SLU, Universidad de Córdoba, Universiteti i Prishtinës, Universitat de Lleida, National Chung Hsing University, German Jordanian University
x	Adviser/consultant/technician	At least 3	Naturland Beratung, Bioland, Bioforum & ILVO Vlaanderen, Innovatiesteunpunt
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
x	Chamber/council of agriculture	2	Chambres d'agriculture - Pays de la Loire, Chambres d'Agriculture de Bretagne
x	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry	4	Bioschwein Austria (organic pigs marketing organisation), Danube Soya Serbia, Prograin Organic, Nutreco (Dutch producer of animal nutrition, fish feed and processed meat products)
x	Farmers & foresters, primary producers	4	Ausumgård, Prodabio, organic pig farmer (France), Gothenborg farmer

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association	15	Soil Association, Demeter, Bio Nouvelle-Aquitaine, AIAB, Bioland, OF&G, Bio en Grand Est, FNAB, UFAB Bio (France), Bioforum (Belgium)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Government	2	Generalitat de Catalunya, Junta de Andalucía
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker	13	11 Innovation Groups of TN OK-Net EcoFeed, Seges (Denmark)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NGO	3	FOAM Organics Europe
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify): private foundations	1	Estonian Organic Farming Foundation
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)	21	Organic Research Centre, ICROFS, FiBL, ILVO Vlaanderen, Innovatiesteunpunt, The Rural Economy and Agricultural Societies
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation	14	FOAM Organics Europe, Ecovalia, Soil Association, ITAB, FNAB, BioForum, AIAB
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		Naturland Beratung
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify): (organic) certification bodies	1	CAAE (Spain)

Networking event number 48

Writing an application for a H2020 multiactor project

Date: 28th May 2020

Location: Aarhus University, Blichers alle 20, 8830 Tjele, Denmark

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): Hohenheim University, Germany; BOKU University of Natural Resources and life Science, Vienna, Austria; LUKE Natural Resources Institute Finland; DCA, Aarhus University, Denmark; ICROFS, Denmark.

Number of participants: 7

Types of participants: Researchers and academic officers

Highlights: In a transnational skype meeting how to include multiactor approach in an application and how to do the stakeholder mapping was discussed. EURAKNOS Thematic Network Explorer's Guide was explained as a solution to write a good application.

Networking included: H2020 project (TN, MA or other): Writing an application

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

Networking event number 49

I2Connect, AgriSpin

Date: n.a.

Location: Utrecht, The Netherlands

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): n.a

Number of participants: n.a.

Types of participants: n.a.

Type of event: bilateral meeting

Highlights: n.a.

Networking included: n.a.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

 Networking event number 50

Chambers of ag

Date: 15/10-2019

Location: Berlin, Germany

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): Chambers of Agriculture

Number of participants in total: 18

Type of networking event²²: Presentation and promotion of EURAKNOS

Highlights: Presentation of EURAKNOS to the representatives of federal chambers of Agriculture of Germany

Networking included the following participant types: n.a.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title)

²² Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

 Networking event number 51

Online discussion about direct sales as an alternative business branch for young farmers

Date: 16.06.2020

Location: online, GoToMeeting, Germany

Participants involved (names of organisations represented):

- NEFERTITI (represented by Grünlandzentrum Niedersachsen / Bremen e.V.)
- NEWBIE (represented by Fachhochschule Soest)
- Main speaker / innovative farmer

Number of participants: 15

Types of participants: Farmers, Researchers, students

Highlights:

- 1) Welcoming
- 2) Interview with Berend Heins about his business Bröös delivery service
- 3) open Question&Answer
- 4) End of event and wrap up with Mentimeter

Networking included: n.a.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xV5HH9cPKpE>

<https://nefertiti-h2020.eu/NefertitiPortal/#!/app-h/eventdetail/393>

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs Towards A European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

The EURAKNOS project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No: 817863

Networking event number 52

DISARM Consortium meeting with external projects

Date: 22-24 June. EURAKNOS mentioned on 23rd.

Location: Online

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): DISARM consortium, representatives from: Healthy Livestock Project, AVANT Project, Enovat Network, Teagasc, OïE, AHDB

Number of participants: 30 approx

Types of participants:

Agricultural levy board, researchers, advisors, farmers organisations, H2020 projects

Highlights: The projects, all based around livestock health and reducing antimicrobial resistance, suggested collaborating and working towards a common thematic website, that could be passed on to future projects covering similar topics in order to help with sustainability, legacy and impact for all projects. I mentioned that EURAKNOS (and EUREKA) are developing guidelines which may be informative to help pursue this aim.

Networking included:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
<input type="checkbox"/> Y	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/> Y	Academic, University & Research		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input type="checkbox"/> Y	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/> Y	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organization		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

 Networking event number 53

Will EURAKNOS be the EUREKA of European Knowledge Exchange

Date: 1/7-2020

Location: Royal Agricultural University, Cirencester, UK

Participants involved: Researchers, lecturers and post graduate agricultural students.

Number of participants: 30

Types of participants: Researchers, lecturers and post graduate agricultural students.

Highlights: An overview of Horizon 20:20, thematic networks and the EURAKNOS and EUREKA projects was presented including key outcomes from PW 2 and 3 of EURAKNOS. A mentimeter poll was used to gather the audiences preferences for dissemination to farmers to compare results to TNs. It was found that this cohort of academics have very similar social media preferences to previous and existing TNs. The Q&A discussion revolved around how RAU can maximise the outputs from EURAKNOS and EUREKA, particularly in KE events with industry and teaching to students. The research seminar was recorded and posted on a gateway page which is available to all academics and post graduate students at RAU. A podcast will be made of the highlights.

FACILITATE
We facilitate and support thematic networks by connecting and extending the current network of thematic networks.

DEVELOP
We develop an EU-wide open source agricultural knowledge innovation database.

COLLECT
We collect knowledge, materials and tools of the thematic networks.

DEVELOP
EU-WIDE OPEN SOURCE AGRICULTURAL KNOWLEDGE INNOVATION DATABASE

COLLECT
EVALUATE AND COMPARE KNOWLEDGE, MATERIALS AND TOOLS

FACILITATE AND SUPPORT THEMATIC NETWORKS
AND CONNECT EXISTING THEMATIC NETWORKS
WIDEN

Go to www.menti.com and use the code 30 70 42

How do you reach farmers & stakeholders?

Channel	Count
Instagram	1
Blogs/forums	5
LinkedIn	1
Emailing	6
Facebook	4
YouTube (videos)	4
Twitter	3
Newsletters	2
Website	3

Networking included:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
<input type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
X	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Networking event number 54

Digital cross-exchange “Sharing farming knowledge and tools: The example of the Organic Farm Knowledge online platform”

Date: 6/7- 2020

Location: Online (GoToTraining)

Participants involved: IFOAM Organics Europe, Soil Association, ICROFS, FiBL, AIAB, ITAB, Ecovalia, ÖMKI, Bioselena, Sementes Vivas, Bio Nouvelle Aquitaine, Biowallonie, Organic Research Centre, Rete Semi Rurali, end users

Number of participants: 26

Types of participants: End users (advisors, researchers, farmers), partners of the platform (farmers’ associations, research centres/institutes, SMEs), TN representatives (OK-Net EcoFeed, OK-Net Arable)

Highlights: Within the framework of EURAKNOS, [Organic Farm Knowledge](#) is frequently mentioned as a good example of an existing electronic knowledge reservoir platform (e-KRP, e.g. in the TN Explorers’ Guide). The online convening was based on the results of the user survey conducted from 8 June to 10 July 2020 (71 responses in total, mainly farmers, researchers, and advisors). Online information was by far the most important source of information for all respondents. The event provided the opportunity to discuss the survey results and provide additional feedback. It revealed that the preference for certain types of tools and social media platforms is country specific and also depends on the target group, thus a distinction should be made between farmers and advisors. A mobile app might be most useful for farmers who do not have a computer close by. Moreover, local farmers are not used to communicate at EU level and might encounter a language barrier, thus national partners should make an effort to select relevant regional tools to translate them into their language. Different topics were introduced to deepen the discussion, asking the participants how the navigation, discussion forum, funding model, and promotion of the platform could be improved. There was general agreement that it should remain free (i.e. open access), but in addition to the open-source tools, trainings could be provided (based on the knowledge produced) for which a fee could be charged. Projects could foresee a budget for the participation in the platform development and to have their outcomes published on the platform (at proposal stage). National (organic) associations and research networks can play a key role in helping to advertise the platform, disseminating it among their target groups.

Networking included: (In the case of some organisations, several types may apply)

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
x	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)	At least 11	EURAKNOS, TN OK-Net EcoFeed (TN OK-Net Arable)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
x	International organisations	5	IFOAM Organics Europe, ICROFS
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
x	Academic, University & Research	2	ICROFS
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
x	Advisory association/company	2	Ecovalia
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers	1	Sementes Vivas (Portugal)
x	Farmers association	7	Bio Nouvelle Aquitaine (France), Rete Semi Rurali (Italian Farmers' Seeds Network), Soil Association (UK), AIAB (Italy), Ecovalia (Spain)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
x	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
x	NGO	3	IFOAM Organics Europe
x	Other (please specify): Foundation	1	Bioselena (Bulgaria)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
x	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)	7	Biowallonie, ORC, ITAB (France), ÖMKI, FiBL
x	Umbrella organisation	6	IFOAM Organics Europe, AIAB, Ecovalia, Soil Association
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
x	Other (please specify): End users	At least 6	

Networking event number 55 (USC)

National Rural Network

Date: 15/9/2020

Location: Online

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): Policy makers, administration, researchers

Number of participants in total: 152 (2 from EURAKNOS)

Type of networking event²³: Online presentation, Q&A and discussion

Highlights: On September 15th, the Spanish national rural network organized an event that brought together different Operating Groups and Innovation Projects, as well as other rural actors not directly related to them (research centers, companies, cooperatives, etc.) but who may be interested in implementing the results obtained, reproducing the project in other territories or being part of a new group or future project. Rosa Mosquera was invited to give a presentation at the event. The AFINET project, but also EUREKA and EURAKNOS were presented and discussed their main objectives and expected outcomes.

²³ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		Not possible to know the number since zoom platform did not allow to check the list of participants
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title):

Figure 1. Poster of the event including title (in Spanish) and organization related info.

Figure 2. Rosa Mosquera was invited to present the AFINET project but also explained her involvement in EURAKNOS and its objectives and expected outcomes.

WEBINAR: Learning and Collaborating across EU projects focused on livestock

Date: 09/09/2020

Location: Online, MS Teams

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): EURAKNOS, DISARM, ROADMAP, Farmomatics, AVANT, FAIRshare, BovINE, 4d4f, Teagasc, EUPig, NEFERTITI, EUREKA, OKNETEcoFeed, HealthyLivestock, NetPoulsafe, Hennovation

Number of participants in total: 30 from Germany, Austria, Belgium, Denmark, France, Norway, the Netherlands, Ireland, UK, Latvia and Romania

Type of networking event²⁴: CEV

Highlights: This CEV took the form of an interactive workshop. Representatives from Thematic Networks (TNs) and other EU projects focused on livestock production had the opportunity to introduce their projects and share their experiences with regards to reaching and impacting end-users. We explored how the tools and knowledge gathered by TNs and other projects can more effectively influence end-users at the farm-level. Informed by outputs from the EURAKNOS project, we considered:

- The multi-actor approach
- Assessing end-user needs for user-friendly knowledge and engagement
- Increasing impact and sustainability
- A common digital platform to store outputs from various projects in one place

We also discussed the current policies and available systems, and constructed some recommendations for improvement.

Agenda

Introductions (5 mins)

Aims of the webinar and the EURAKNOS project (10 mins)

5-minute flash presentations (25 mins) from:

- FAIRshare
- DISARM
- AVANT
- BovINE
- 4D4F

Facilitated discussion (45 mins) on the following topics:

- How to promote user-engagement?
- How to increase impact and sustainability?
- Potential scope for a common platform

²⁴ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

- Feedback for the EC to help support projects in these areas

Wrap-up of the meeting and discussion (5 mins)

After brief introductions, the EURAKNOS project was presented to the participants. This short presentation included a summary of EURAKNOS' aims, the partners involved and key outputs: Explorer's guide and common platform. Also mentioned that the work is being further developed by EUREKA.

The aim of the facilitated discussion was to generate feedback which EURAKNOS can incorporate into their outputs, for example their Policy Brief and a selection of Practice Abstracts.

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title):

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs Towards A European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

1

Write down your ideas for each stakeholder based on the different potential categories of solutions

	Farmers	Advisors	Researchers	Policy makers and supply chain actors
Digitally	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> meetings using interactive tools - like mural! Online forums to ask questions and share tips Whats app groups to keep on energy and nutrition between meetings Video case studies showing a farmer or farmer group from different regions Youtube 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ERBS European Roundtable for Beef Sustainability EIP Agri SCAR standing committee for ag research
In person/1-2-1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ability to pay farmers for sharing their experience Be sure to follow up and show how the info/exchange from the farmer is being used! 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ability to pay advisors for their time 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contacts identified through thematic networks and other EU projects 	
In person/group events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maximum use of interactive workshops Using participatory tools and principles Be sure each farmer shows his good practices and gets back to home with new solutions Share facts where farmers have the opportunity to showcase an idea or action or innovative solution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Multi actor farm health plans - working together towards common goals Involve the Regions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Multi actor farm health plans - working together towards common goals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EAAP (European Federation of Animal Science) special sessions e.g. ATF (Animal Task Force)
Via existing organisations and networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Include farmer facing organisations in the network consortia ENRD - European Network for Rural Dev and national ones Coope Cogeca EIP Agri 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use EPRAS (European Forum for Rural Advisory Services) and GFRAS (Global Forum for Rural Advisory Services) networks EIP Agri 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Groups such as European Assoc of Animal Production (EAAP) EIP Agri
Wildcard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wildcard 			

MURAL exercise: How can we improve user engagement?

How might we increase our impact?

How might we improve the sustainability and legacy of EU H2020 TN/multi-actor projects?

MURAL Exercise: How can we increase our impact and improve the sustainability and legacy of EU H2020 TN/MA projects

What do we want the knowledge platform/database to be? What do we want it to look like?

1

Map out your thoughts about how a common knowledge platform/database could work.

MURAL Exercise: What do we want the knowledge platform/database to be? What do we want it to look like?

MURAL Exercise: recommendations for the EC to support more effective TN/MA projects to achieve maximal impact and sustainability

NW 10 Scottish virtual demo event

Date: 2/11/2020

Location: Online

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): GLZ, Nefertiti TN, Susan Pirie Senior Agricultural Consultant and Area Manager, SAC Consulting (SAC is a division of Scotland's rural college) Dr Annie McKee, Social, Economic and Geographical Sciences, The James Hutton Institute, Scotland, GLZ (GLower Saxony, germany) Sandra Honegger and Elodie Pascal, Alizee Chouteau (Idele, France), John Moriarty (Teagasc, Ireland), Malcolm Mac Donald (SAC, UK)+ farmers/crofters mainly from Scotland

Number of participants in total: 42 (2 from EURAKNOS)

Type of networking event²⁵: CEV (online) - NW 10 Scottish virtual demo event

Highlights: Presentation of EURAKNOS and facilitated discussion so as to write Practice Abstracts on best practices shared during the online session

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title):

²⁵ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
<input type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)	2	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research	2	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company	4	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers	29	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association	3	NFUS (National Farmers Union Scotland)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)	2	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

 Networking event number 58

How to foster peer to peer exchange in viticulture

Date: 30/6-2020

Location: Virtual meeting on Teams. Host in France

Participants involved (names of organisations represented):

Name	Institute	Country	Network
Léa Tourneur	ACTA	France	EURAKNOS
Nicolas Aveline	IFV	France	NEFERTITI
Maude Lewis	IFV	France	INNOSETA
Marion Enard	CA 33	France	NEFERTITI
Eric Serrano	IFV	France	WINETWORK
Eric Mazzani	Univ Torino	Italy	INNOSETA
Paolo Balsari	Univ Torino	Italy	INNOSETA
Fabrizio Giolli	Univ Torino	Italy	INNOSETA
Adam Hegyi	EKU	Hungary	WINETWORK
Gianni Trioli	VINIDEA	Italy	WINETWORK/AGRILINK/ PLAID
Fanny Prezman	IFV	France	EURAKNOS/WINETWORK
Eirios Hugo	IFV	France	EURAKNOS/INNOSETA

Number of participants in total: 12

Type of networking event²⁶: CEV

Highlights: After a short introduction of meeting objective and the tools used, participants presented themselves through an icebreaker organized on Zeetings (www.zeetings.com/CEV-meeting/0009-9867-0002)

The responses are presented below:

What is your name, organism and expertise ? [10 responses](#)

Frequency	Response
1	Maude lewis, ifv, engineer
1	Nicolas aveline, ifv , grapevine protection
1	Eirios hugo-ifv-r&d in viticulture and oenology

²⁶ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

- 1 Léa tourneur, acta, in charge of european affairs
- 1 Marion, chambre d'agriculture, vineyard consultant
- 1 Gianni trioli, vinidea, dissemination
- 1 Ádám hegyi, eku hungary, viticulture and oenology
- 1 Paolo balsari unito
- 1 Eric_mozzanini_____unito_____european project
- 1 Eric Serrano, IFV, regional manager

1) Where are you from ? [10 responses](#)

Frequency	Ratio	Response
3	30 %	Italy
6	60 %	France
1	10 %	Hungary

2) In which project / TN / OG are you working in ? [10 responses](#)

Frequency	Ratio	Response
3	19%	Innoseta
3	19%	Winetwork
2	12%	Optima
3	19%	Nefertiti
1	6%	Euraknos
1	6%	Disarm
1	6%	Panacea
1	6%	I2connect
1	6%	Ipmworks

Then, Léa Tourneur from Acta presented EURAKNOS project (presentation in appendix)

Round table on cross-visits experiences

Nefertiti - Marion Enard (Agriculture Chamber of Gironde -Bordeaux area)

- Description of the CEV experience:

Thematic of the CV: Reduction of plant protection products: 5 countries – 2 demonstrations in one day in the Bordeaux area.

25 participants: farmers

Stimulation of exchanges with a prerequisite canvas of questions

- Difficulties: language, hot weather, to maintain concentration during a whole day
- Challenge: create a good atmosphere to facilitate exchanges
- Recommendations: 2 demonstrations in one day is too much → Marion Enard recommended to held one demonstration in the morning, over 2 days
- Result: Good feedback of participants, Good exchanges

Innoseta – Maud Lewis (IFV- French Wine and Vine Institute)

- Description of the CEV experience:

Regional and transnational workshops around spraying innovation techniques in all types of crops. — Demonstration in field then workshop in small groups (3 thematic groups : needs of farmers, innovations to promote) with interactive tool (beekast) enabling to rank the innovations presented according to interest of participants

Innovations are presented in an online platform www.innoseta.eu

130 participants; 16% of foreign participants, advisors, universities, administration, advisors, technician, sprayer manufacturers companies

- Duration: one day with a mix of demonstrations of sprayers and wind simulator for drift measurement
- Difficulties: the interactive tool was not ideal to foster direct exchanges...
- Recommendations: for each group, it is nice to have several facilitators (one speaker, one collecting answers on the interactive tool)

Agrilink - Plaid - IoF2020 + Oenoforum – Gianni Trioli (Vinidea):

- Description of the CEV experience:

How advisors can improve knowledge exchange: It is different to talk with farmers or with advisors/prescriptors. They have different perceptions and different timing in decisions.

How to involve farmers/ wine growers? Easier to talk and disseminate knowledge to advisers or opinion leader than farmers. These people could then disseminate knowledge to farmers.

- Recommendations:
 - More effective to talk to opinion leaders, advisors or prescriptors, difficulty to reach directly the farmer
 - Peer to peer is nice but also dangerous if there is no expert in the discussions
 - Experience of increasing usefulness of virtual meetings (to stimulate interaction: use chat, voice, interactive tools,...)
 - Topic involving the more people are daily practices. People are not coming to the event if they are not interested in the subject. Focus on practical subject with daily difficulties for farmers (could be very simple)
- Difficulties:

- time, especially for farmers
- Difficult to involve people if they don't know the technique presented (hard uptake of innovation)
- Weather for presential meetings

A solution could be online meetings. Experience on online meetings with up to 600 participants

- Duration for online meetings: 40 minutes of presentation, then 1 to 2 h discussions.
- Virtual demo (even in a non-professional way) raise a lot of exchanges by using all possible tools
- Limitation could be the access to the network, competences in computing

Common facts in Cross visits organized by partners:

The experiences related by the partner showed a mix of demonstration and workshops.

These event are from one day to 2 or 3 hours duration for online CEV (ideally duration should be 1h30/2h maximum).

Targets of events are in majority technicians and winegrowers rather than policy makers or students

Main differences between cross visits organized:

According to the cross-visit and its topic, participants are farmers and/or international audience. Cross-visit could reach a high amount of people and can be adapted to different targets.

Size of the group: small group (25 participants), big group (130 participants), online workshop (up to 600 participants)

Ideas collected from the workshop:

- Use interactive tools (beekcast, mural,...)
- Prepare canvas with questions to ask before the CEV
- Go totally virtual for more impact (with videos, char, voice presentations, multilingual webinars, etc.)
- Use innovative formats like podcasts (for farmers to listen to them during their tractor work for instance)

Common difficulties:

- Difficult to find a common language, especially for non-native speakers
- Time (specifically for farmers) and money need for participation (travel)
- Planning the event at the right time (farmers are very dependent on weather conditions so their participation can be postponed at the last minute)
- Difficult to introduce very new topics (people tend to be interested in topics they already know about – hard innovation uptake)

At the end of the round-table recommendation for organizing future activities were highlighted.

Recommendations for future cross-exchanges activities:

- Do not organize workshop in agricultural fairs (difficult for farmers to focus on workshop if there are full of parallel events)
- Focus on discussions and human contact and not tools in virtual or physical meetings
- Keep it short!
- Involve opinion leaders, advisors, key experts
- Peer to peer is nice but sometimes dangerous: keep an expert in there to keep on track with technical realities

- Go virtual for more impact? (more availability of opinion leaders and speakers) Covid crisis has opened new opportunities; recommended duration: 1h30 max; produce videos (professional or not) to compensate the lack of physical demonstrations

Participative session 1: Best tools for fostering peer to peer exchange of knowledge

This participative session was held on Mural (app.mural.co).

Participants were asked to fill sticky notes with possible tools to reach 4 targets: winegrowers, technicians, students and policy makers. Then to link target with tools using arrows, one or several tools for specific targets to deliver a certain type of information. Discussion around the result last for 10 minutes.

Stimulating knowledge exchange

Participative session 2: Topics for future cross-exchanges or thematic networks

In this second participative session, participants identified possible topics for future exchange. Either urgent needs for farmers or lack of information. A voting session enabled to prioritize the most important subjects for the sector.

Exercise 2

Thematics for future cross-visit or TN in viticulture

Results of the voting session

Exercise 2

Thematics for future cross-visit or TN in viticulture

Top “hot topics” for future thematic networks or cross visits in viticulture:

- Vineyard soils: potential of biodiversity of soils for researchers and practitioners. This topic shows growing awareness and increases concern about high amounts of knowledge to be disseminated.
- Climate change: opportunity to organize Cross Exchange Visits with countries already confronted to climate change
- Innovative grapevine disease management to reduce use of plant protection products: new tools (disrupting systems, grapevine cover, tunnels), increase innovation uptake, multicrop aspects
- Organic viticulture to organic wine production: reduce use of copper, soil management, management in different countries-geographic areas. A TN could focus on problems raised in organic viticulture and by confronting different techniques used in different countries.

The meeting was closed with the presentation of Euraknos explorer’s guide.

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title)

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs Towards A European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

Pictures of the participants of the CEV

Networking event number 59

Digital cross-exchange “Designing innovation projects databases”

Date: 18/6-2020

Location: Online

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): Representatives of Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Service, Estonian Organic Farming Foundation, SITES, NGO Põllukultuuride klaster, NGO Estonian Dairy Cluster, EIP-Agri Service Point, The Dutch Network Support Unit, Latvian Rural Advisory and Training Centre, Agricultural Research Centre, ICROFS, Gent University, Estonian Rural Development Foundation, Scottish Government, Scottish Rural Network, Teagasc, Polish Agricultural Advisory Service, NGO Liivimaa Lihaveis.

Number of participants in total: 23

Type of participants: EURAKNOS partners, National Rural Network support units, innovation projects, partners Thematic Networks (SKIN, BOWINE), international contacts of Estonian NSU.

The participants of the webinar were hand-picked to reduce the time to spend on the kick-off to the theme. The participants represented several organisations and countries. Many NRN support units represent also advisory or innovation support services, the TN representatives come from universities and research units, the OG representatives are involved in different innovation projects (incl TN) and some represented farmers. The participants represented Belgium, Denmark, Estonia, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, the Netherlands, Poland, Scotland/UK, Spain.

Type of networking event²⁷: CEV

Highlights: The online event brought together NRN partners to focus on the design of websites/databases of innovation projects and their practices. The aim of the webinar was to compare the ways of presenting information about innovative projects. Special attention was given to national rural network databases. The webinar was directly linked to EURAKNOS, which looks deeply into electronic knowledge reservoirs. The seminar started with the short presentation of the aims of EURAKNOS. Four project databases – EIP-AGRI Service Point; Dutch, Latvian and Estonian NSU – presented their process and hopes on the development of the websites and seminar continued with discussion. The discussion was grouped to three areas: 1) process – how the style and content were designed; 2) selection – was there a selection of the projects/examples and what were the reasons; 3) visual – what was considered when choosing the visualisation.

Learning points:

- A question that was raised during the discussion, was that we talk about databases but are we sure we are all talking about the same thing? Participants of the CEV have the feeling that often when we talked about databases of innovation examples, the reality of it is just a catalogue of projects. Some of the participants said that a database should allow automatic extraction of information and sending it to users.

²⁷ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

- One of the most difficult tasks is picking the brain of the target group – what do they want out of the database? In order to find out what the target group wants from the database, you must first know who your target group is. Depending if your target is e.g. farmers, advisors or public officials, the needs may vary. The catalogue of projects is interesting for the project managers, but farmers need rather the results and lessons.
- The NSU databases shown during the CEV were for innovation projects so there were no specific criteria for the selection of projects. Every project, which the website owners thought relevant regarding the innovation process (TN, OG or else), were described in local languages.
- Surprisingly the language didn't come up as a big issue during the discussion. This may be due to the fact, that the participants of the CEV were more advanced users of databases and they all are familiar with the English language.
- The appearance of a database must be catchy and easily understandable. On this matter, the EIP-AGRI database is seen as too complicated. The fact that you can't connect the EIP-AGRI database to any national or local databases, is also seen as a shortfall. As there are a lot of projects, the search engine must be efficient. And for this, having a good system for keywords is really important. The EURAKNOS project is looking into this topic.

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
x	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)	12	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
x	Operational group	6	
x	International organisations	4	
x	National Rural Networks	7	
x	Innovation Networks	4	
x	Academic, University & Research	2	
x	Adviser/consultant/technician	4	
x	Advisory association/company	3	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
x	Farmers & foresters, primary producers	2	
x	Farmers association	1	
x	Government	1	
x	Innovation broker	2	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
x	NGO	5	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		

<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title)

Why are you interested in this session about innovation databases?

I think it is quite important to benchmark and learn from the experience of others.

Because we are not sharing truly I am looking to this database from both sides - as user and provider of information

To catch ideas

13 Responses

Recent changes

EUROOPA PROJEKTID: Maaelu ja -poliitika

Aadress: Maaeluvõrgustik
20. märts 2018. a

Maaelu ja -poliitika

enabling Enhance New Approaches in BioBased Local Innovation Networks for Growth

Temaatiline võrgustik **ENABLING** (detsember 2017 - november 2020) käsitleb uusi lähenemisviise kohalikes biopõhistes innovatsioonivõrgustikes. Temaatiline võrgustiku eesmärk on arendada biopõhise tootmise potentsiaali, edendades biopõhiste toodete tootmiseks kõhnade lammehalate tootmist. Selleks pakutakse vahendeid ja meetodeid, mis soodustavad koostööd ja teadmiste vahetamist sektoris.

KORRALDUSE

Kõik soovituskoostöötegevuste eesmärgid saavutati:

- selgitati välja, et lühemaajaliseks ajaks maaelutehnoloogiliseks osutatakse parema tulemuse kui koostööpartnerite ja teiste kättesaadavate vahendite abil teha järele.
- selgitati välja Eesti lühemaajaliseks ajaks maaelutehnoloogiliseks osutatakse, milleks loodi FF Hõbe
- selgitati, et lühemaajaliseks ajaks maaelutehnoloogiliseks osutatakse ja seeläbi tehti veel kasutatavaid vahendeid lühemaajaliseks ajaks.
- määrati koostöötegevuste eesmärgid maaelutehnoloogiliseks ajaks.
- määrati maaelutehnoloogiliseks ajaks lühemaajaliseks ajaks 13-osaliseks (ühikute arvust)
- tehti koostöötegevuste lühemaajaliseks ajaks 13-osaliseks (ühikute arvust)
- määrati koostöötegevuste lühemaajaliseks ajaks 13-osaliseks (ühikute arvust)
- määrati koostöötegevuste lühemaajaliseks ajaks 13-osaliseks (ühikute arvust)

Selleks, et maaelutehnoloogiliseks ajaks võrgustiku tegevuste arendamiseks võtta ette, mis võimaldab teha koostööd ja teadmiste vahetamist sektoris.

"Maailm on meie ühine, me kõik oleme selle osa ja sellel on meie ühine vastutus." - Martin Luther King

EURAKNOS CEV
by Hanna Tamás

3 - Style/ visual of the databases
Repetitions - Differences - Suggestions

Many end-users are preferring personalized approach

Video, or audio introduction. This as a way to entice users to come into the project description.

Visual content management is extra cost but should be done. Farmers most interested in innovation are young, everything needs to be visually attractive

8 Responses

Networking event number 60

59th IALB Conference and 9th EUFRAS Conference and 11th GFRAS Annual Meeting

Date: 5-6/10-2020

Location: Online event

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): From the side of EURAKNOS, the project was represented by the Agricultural University of Athens (AUA) and Hercules Panoutsopoulos. There is no information about the whole list of the conference participants.

Number of participants: approximately: 20

Types of participants: Advisors, policy makers, H2020 project representatives, probably farmers/farmer representatives

Highlights: The 59th IALB Conference, 9th EUFRAS Conference, and the 11th GFRAS Annual Meeting constitute a cluster of meetings that were organised and delivered as an online event by EUFRAS. The conference was made up of plenary sessions and workshops with the plenary sessions being devoted to presentations delivered from keynote speakers. The workshop sessions took place both on the 5th and the 6th of October in order to provide more options and a greater flexibility to the conference's audience. AUA delivered a workshop in EURAKNOS (both on the 5th and 6th of October) focused on the issues relating to the labour-intensive tasks needed to be performed when designing and developing a centralised data repository, as well as in the context of collecting relevant data objects and integrating them into the repository. The two workshop sessions were attended by a total number of 20 attendees, who, in their majority, were advisors and representatives of other H2020 projects. The attendees showed a great interest in the presented work and the feedback provided by them was positive. It also needs to be noticed that one of the two workshop sessions was attended from two representatives of the Best4Soil TN, who agreed on a number of issues stressed as important (namely, the careful definition of metadata, the need to carefully address IPR issues and the sustainability of such repository development – related efforts).

Networking included:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

There is no information about the number of participants per each of the above selected attendee categories. Total number of participants: **~20**.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

Networking event number 61

EIP-AGRI Online Seminar - CAP Strategic Plans: The key role of Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) in Member States

Date: 08-09/10-2020

Location: Online event

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): From the side of EURAKNOS, the projects (both EURAKNOS and EUREKA) were represented by Gent University and Pieter Spanoghe. Other participants: Research and Innovation, DG AGRI, EIP-AGRI Service Point, Innovatiesteunpunt (BE), Ministry of Agriculture (HU), AKIS International (ES), Teagasc (IE), Federation of Swedish Farmers and Copa-Cogeca (SE), Chamber of Agriculture in Schleswig-Holstein (DE), EU Commissioner for Agriculture and Rural Development, Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development in Poland, Institute of Natural Resources and Agrobiology of Salamanca (IRNASA) (ES), Chamber of Agriculture and Forestry of Slovenia (SI), Adept Foundation (RO), Agricultural Advisory Centre in Brwinów (PL), National Rural Network Unit (NL), Lithuanian Agricultural Advisory Service (LT), University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine Cluj Napoca (RO), Institute of Agrifood Research and Technology – IRTA (ES), IDELE (FR), National Rural Network Unit (DE), CEJA, RDP Managing Authority (SE), National Rural Network (IE), Estonian Dairy Cluster (EDC) (EE), National Rural Network (AT), CIHEAM-IAMM, the Mediterranean Intergovernmental Agronomic Institute – Montpellier (FR), Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ES), Ministry of Rural Affairs (EE), Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality (NL).

Number of participants: approximately: 30

Types of participants: Researchers, Advisors, Policy makers, farmers associations

Highlights: The overall aim of this seminar is to support the Member States in the preparation of their AKIS Strategic Plans and to promote efficient agricultural knowledge flows across the whole EU. It will focus on exchanging experiences and inspiring examples in organising and supporting knowledge creation and exchange in agriculture between the different AKIS actors. It will create the opportunity to familiarise Member State administrations and other AKIS actors with the various possible approaches through discussions and the exchange of experiences on draft AKIS Strategic Plans and actions.

Networking included:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

There is no information about the number of participants per each of the above selected attendee categories. Total number of participants: ~30.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

Networking event number 62

International Agriculture Symposium

Date: 08-09/10- 2020

Location: Online event

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): From the side of EURAKNOS, a specific aspect of communication (the use of social media in TNs) was represented by Gent University and Elena Feo. There is no information about the whole list of the conference participants.

Number of participants: approximately: 20

Types of participants: Researchers, Advisors, probably policy makers.

Highlights:

The International Agricultural Symposium is an annual platform for international scientific discussion on agriculture, food, rural development, environment and forestry. This event represented a good opportunity to exchange ideas, to strengthen existing and to create new academic networks, and to foster dialogue between the academia, public institutions, the private sector and civil society organizations on the recent global and regional trends in the agro-food sector. Multidisciplinary results reported during the event, will contribute to the dissemination of knowledge and good practices to all actors of the agro-food chain (e.g. farmers, extension agents, researchers, policy makers) as well as the general public about the importance of agriculture and food science, one of the most important strategic areas of many national research strategies. In this framework, UGent presented a specific aspect of EURAKNOS: “Communication, dissemination and the use of social media in H2020 Thematic Networks”. The attendees showed interest in the presented work and the feedback provided by them was positive.

Networking included:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
<input type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

There is no information about the number of participants per each of the above selected attendee categories. Total number of participants: ~20.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

EURAKNOS CEV: Agroforestry and climate change innovations

Date: 15/10-2020^h

Location: Virtual meeting on Microsoft Teams. Host in Spain.

Participants involved (names of organisations represented):

Name	Institute	Country	Network
Tsegazeab Zegeye	Norwegian Church Aid	Norway	
Hannes Hohensinner	HLBLA St. Florian	Austria	
Margarita Avgerinou		Greece	
Zuzana Spakova	Freelance	Czech Republic	
Md. Seikh Sadiul Islam Tanvir	Khulna University	Bangladesh	
Fatma Aribi	Arid Regions Institute of Medenine Tunisia	Tunisia	
Henri Husson	crpf nouvelle aquitaine	France	
Iván Rodríguez	ASOPORCEL	Spain	AFINET / OG - Effect of the farming system and age at slaughter in the characteristics of the meat of celtic pigs / OG- New systems of handling and implementation of a classification system of Celtic pig meat / Pilot Project (PP) – silvopastoral use with Celtic pig through modular, transportable and autonomous system/ PP– Use of Celtic pig fat fractions to obtain different meat products / PP – Incorporation of high oleic corn in the production of differentiated quality Celtic pig
Vanessa Álvarez López	University of Santiago de Compostela - USC	Spain	AFINET/Open2Preserve
Zannati Yeasmin	Khulna University	Bangladesh	
Eduard Mauri	EFI	Spain	INCREDIBLE
Linus Linse	Agroforestry Sweden	Sweden	
Julie Rohde Birk	Organic Denmark/EURAF	Denmark	
Jaime Coello	Forest Science and Technology Center of Catalonia (CTFC)	Spain	
Jürgen Rieger	University BOKU Vienna	Austria	
Ali Nawaz	University of Sargodha	Pakistan	
Teresa Fidalgo Fonseca	Universidade de Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro	Portugal	OG - Afforestation of Agricultural Land with More Forestry, Pasture, Innovation and Value (FTA+siv)

Andrew Szunyogh	Szunyogh Family Farm	Hungary	Organic cattle breeding in Zala county
Sondes Fkiri	Inrgref	Tunisia	
Marina Castro	Instituto Politécnico de Bragança	Portugal	OG - Afforestation of Agricultural Land with More Forestry, Pasture, Innovation and Value (FTA+siv)
Claudia Cordovil	Instituto Superior de Agronomia da Universidade de Lisboa	Portugal	
Maria Ernfors	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences	Sweden	
David Almeida			
Rafael Pompa	University of Reading	UK	
Roberto Rubio	CESEFOR	Spain	
Elsa Lagerquist	Agroforestry Sweden	Sweden	
Shebeshe Haile	Free University of Bolzano	Italy	
Rita Almeida	CEF - Centro de Estudos Florestais	Portugal	
Ana Filipa Guia	Instituto Superior de Agronomia (ISA) – U. Lisboa	Portugal	OG - Afforestation of Agricultural Land with More Forestry, Pasture, Innovation and Value (FTA+siv)
Divina Vázquez Varela	University of Santiago de Compostela - USC	Spain	AFINET/Go-Grass/Open2Preserve
Manuel de Brito Caldeira Bugalho		Portugal	
Kalliopi Stara	University of Ioannina	Greece	
María Rosa Mosquera Losada	University of Santiago de Compostela - USC	Spain	AFINET/EURAKNOS/EUREKA/Go-Grass/Open2Preseve
Francisco Javier Rodríguez Rigueiro	University of Santiago de Compostela - USC	Spain	AFINET/EURAKNOS/EUREKA/Go-Grass

Number of participants in total: 34

Type of networking event²⁸: Webinar on Thematic Networks and Operational Groups.

Highlights: The Spanish Cross-Exchange of Knowledge on Agroforestry event has been organized within the EURAKNOS Project scope and objectives aiming at providing information on the implementation and maintenance on time (even once funding is over) of the Thematic Networks (TNs) and the Operational Groups (OGs). The event was entitled “Agroforestry and climate change

²⁸ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

innovations”. The event was co-organized with EFIMED, the Mediterranean facilities of the European Forest Institute (EFI) being Eduard Mauri the contact person. The event was circulated through the EURAKNOS and AFINET Social Networks (being shared multiple times and reaching, according to FB stats, 2500 people just in this platform). There were 83 people registered to the event, being 34 the final number of attendees coming from 15 different countries (Figure 1).

Countries and share of representation according to Spanish CEV of EURAKNOS attendees origin.

The event started by presenting the agenda of the event (Figure 2), focused on networking promotion through TNs and OGs experiences. Thus, Rosa Mosquera (EURAKNOS WP2 leader) started introducing EURAKNOS to the audience including its goals and the outcomes expected related to TNs improvement and promotion. Following this introductory part, Eduard Mauri (EFI) shared with the audience EFI experience managing a non-wood-forest products related TN as INCREDIBLE, the project was explained and later on he focused on identifying strengths and weaknesses linked to the involvement of different actors in the project. Later, Rosa Mosquera employed a similar approach with the agroforestry linked TN AFINET, its outcomes and participants feedback according to its results. Besides the TNs presentations, the Operational Groups (OGs) were also a capital part of this event since, as networks, collaboration among different actors are developed. Thus, three OGs based on agroforestry implementation were presented, one from Portugal, “Afforestation of Agricultural Land with More Forestry, Pasture, Innovation and Value (FTA+siv)”, and two from the Spanish region of Galicia (“Effect of the farming system and age at slaughter in the characteristics of the meat of Celtic pigs” and “New systems of handling and implementation of a classification system of Celtic pork meat”).

- 10:00-10:10 Welcome
- 10:10-10:30 INCREDIBLE Project (Eduard Mauri - EFI)
- 10:30-10:50 AFINET Project (Rosa Mosquera - USC)
- 10:50-11:05 Silvopastoral Portuguese OG (Marina Castro - IPB)
- 11:05-11:25 Celtic Pigs OGs (Iván Rodríguez - ASOPORCEL)
- 11:25-12:00 Interactive session – Q&A

Spanish CEV agenda

The Portuguese OG experience was explained by Marina Castro, from the Instituto Politécnico de Bragança (IPB) while the Spanish OGs on silvopastoralism with Celtic pig were depicted by Iván Rodríguez, manager of ASOPORCEL, the association of Celtic pigs breeders of Galicia.

Presentation of the TN INCREDIBLE, performed by Eduard Mauri (EFI)

Once the aforementioned TNs and OGs outcomes and experiences on networking were presented, an interactive session started together with the Q&A. To allow the public to take part in this session, a presentation was prepared by using the Mentimeter tool. This session was conducted by splitting three different rounds of questions according to attendees profiling purposes, networking issues and knowledge reservoirs.

The first question was related with the mentimeter validation and to allow participants to get used to it and we asked about the participant’s organization types. Half of the participants claimed to work in a national level institutions/organizations, while the other half of the participants were equally distributed between international and local institutes/organizations. A majority of participants claimed to be linked with academic or research institutions and, therefore, the majority indicated that research/technical centre and advisory is their working area. Advisors, NGO and umbrella associations were also represented in a minor proportion (Figure 4).

Type of organizations that participants claimed being linked to

Half of the respondents were involved in H2020 projects, Focus Groups or National Rural Networks while the rest of the participants were not, probably associated to those from outside of Europe.

When asked about networking, most of the participants responded that sustainable forest land use would be better acquired through knowledge exchange among actors (Figure 5). Asked about how can we enhance networking among forest actors, participants mentioned ideas like promoting dialogue, field visits, promote experiences in the field with successful farms, organizing frequent meetings, seminars at farm level, conferences or symposiums, engaging policymakers on the field or podcasts. Asked about how to enhance knowledge exchange, respondents mentioned several times training activities such as field visits, workshops, meetings and, furthermore, to create a clear hub of knowledge and maximize the importance of professionals as Innovation brokers, who can connect all the ideas and need of the different actors. On the other hand, it was not easy for participants to provide ideas on how to improve networking among forest actors and NRNs to move forward policy being associations a key component reflected by participants responses. Asked about the most relevant tools to enlarge forest actors networking, social networks highlighted as the favourite tool for participants.

Best ways to achieve sustainable forest land use according to Agroforestry CEV participants as percentage of total answers.

The session on knowledge reservoirs started asking about the best knowledge transfer tools to improve land-use sustainability. Living labs, field visits, best practice examples, videos and dissemination appeared as suggestions made by CEV participants. Furthermore, respondents clearly stated knowledge reservoirs are useful to acquire sustainability of the land and almost all of them expressed their willingness to update information in a knowledge reservoir. Finally, some of the main tools or key points attendees expect in a knowledge reservoir are the accuracy of the information, multilanguage, keywords, recorded presentations, easy access, authors contact possibility etc. (Figure 6).

Suggestions made on the main tools participants expect from a knowledge reservoir

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)	6	One participant could cover several types*
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)	1	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Operational group	5	
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations	3	
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks	2	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks	5	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research	18	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician	4	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers	1	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker	1	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks	2	
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO	1	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)	10	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation	2	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training	1	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title)

Conclusions: The event can be considered a success due to the diverse and large number of participants we had. With regard to the two focused topics of the meeting discussed under the forest and agroforestry umbrella: knowledge exchange and knowledge reservoir we can conclude the following:

Knowledge exchange: The knowledge exchange is promoted through the increase of actors exchange and therefore the networking associated to participatory activities such as dialogue, field visits,

frequent meetings. However, conferences/symposiums are more adequate for policy makers/actors exchanges.

The knowledge exchange is facilitated by the development of a knowledge reservoir, and the existence of innovation brokers facilitating networking. Associations are seen as key to contact with the NRN while social media is seen as essential to enlarge networks

The best knowledge transfer tools to improve land-use sustainability are linked to living labs, field bists but also to the existence of knowledge reservoirs where best practices or videos are available.

Knowledge reservoirs

Forest and agroforestry actors find accuracy, multi-lingual, easy access, and audiovisual material availability as key aspects for developing a useful knowledge reservoirs but also to have the possibility to contact with the authors of the different materials. The participants mentioned that they are willing to update information once the knowledge reservoir is created.

Networking event number 64

Online event: cross exchange between EURAKNOS and EUROSHEEP TN

Date: 25/11/2020

Location: Online, Zoom + Klaxoon

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): EURAKNOS (IDELE + GLZ), SHEEPNET & EUROSHEEP (NEIKER – Spain / TEAGASC – Ireland / SRUC – UK / IDELE – France / AGRIS – Italy / HAO – Greece / TOGEN – Turkey)

Number of participants in total: 11

Type of networking event²⁹: CEV

Highlights: All the national network facilitators were invited by the coordinator of EUROSHEEP to participate to this cross-exchange between EURAKNOS and EUROSHEEP.

The objectives were to engage discussions and exchange on the common issues related to communication and mainly dissemination that a Thematic Network has to deal with, in a way to find efficient practical solutions. This CEV took the form of a series of interactive workshops. We explored together how to proceed to disseminate with success the TNs outputs. It was also an opportunity to promote the explorer's guide of EURAKNOS.

Agenda

Introduction: Aims of the webinar

Who attend this CE today? (10 min)

10-minute flash presentations (20 min) from EURAKNOS and EUROSHEEP projects

Facilitated workshops on the following topics:

- Sharing and dissemination (10 mins workshop on Klaxoon)
- Good practices for dissemination (25 mins workshop on Klaxoon)
- Measuring impact (25 mins workshop on Klaxoon)
- (Enhancing sustainability) : a short PPT presentation

Wrap-up of the CE and evaluation (15 mins):

- What does each participant take back home?
- Individual evaluation on this CE workshops

²⁹ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title):

Get ready for this CE between EURAKNOS and EUROSHEEP

Networking event number 65

CEV on Networking

Date: 19/11-2020

Location: Online hosted by ICROFS/AU, Denmark

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): Coordinators from Thematic Networks: AGRI-SPIN, I2connect, EU-FRUIT, HNV-LINK, Legumes translated, SheepNet, BovINE, EUROSHEEP, SMARTPROTECT, INNOSETA, NEWBIE, and two facilitators with advanced skills on networks and communication. One is also a coordinator of I2connect.

Number of participants in total: 13

Type of networking event³⁰: CEV

Highlights: The CEV meeting focused on exchange of knowledge on networking, including networking online in times when physical meetings are not possible. Coordinators from 10 different Thematic Networks participated. Two persons were invited to facilitate and stimulate the exchange of knowledge on networking and the processes behind networking. In the beginning of the meeting, ICROFS presented the EURAKNOS project (main goals, Explorers guide, the four pillars of the EURAKNOS HIKR design and how TN's can utilize the EURAKNOS database) and the outcome for EURAKNOS of the meeting.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title):

³⁰ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

Picture from exercise with Mural.

Picture from exercise with Mural.

What was important for you?

Picture from exercise with Mentimeter.

Digital CEV with facilitator agents of NEFERTITI

Date: 9/10-2020

Location: Online

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): Bastiaansen, Leanne <l.bastiaansen@aeres.nl>; Rita Melis <rita.melis@ispaam.cnr.it>; Nilla Nilsdotter-Linde <Nilla.Nilsdotter-Linde@slu.se>; Anna CARLSSON <carlsson@skogsgard.se>; Fergus Bogue <Fergus.Bogue@teagasc.ie>; Artur Paszkowski <artur.paszowski@up.poznan.pl>; Andrzej Przepiora <a.przepiora@wir.org.pl>; Daniel JACQUET <djacquet@awenet.be>; Gauder Patrik <pgauder@awenet.be>; Benoit Delaite <b.delaite@trame.be>; Fanny Baste-Sauvaire <fanny.baste@apca.chambagri.fr>; ANNA CZERWI?SKA <a.czerwinska@wir.org.pl>; Mairhofer, Franziska <Franziska.Mairhofer@laimburg.it>; Lorenzo Pascarella <pascarella.l@aia.it>; Hoellrigl, Philipp <Philipp.Hoellrigl@laimburg.it>; Fradin Julien <Julien.Fradin@idele.fr>; Hein de Kort <hdkort@ltonoord.nl>
Elodie Pascal, Jendrik Holthusen, Hanna Vagt (GLZ)

Number of participants in total: 19

Type of networking event³¹: Experience sharing (CEV)

Highlights:

Cross Exchange 2020	
5 min	Introduction of the seminar
10 min	Introduction round
15 min	Presentation of Euraknos project
15 min	Measuring impact e.g. drone use in grassland farming
40 min	Knowledge Exchange (Discussion) The functional channels for reaching endusers? What kind of Soft Skill Training are needed? Best way to intergrate the traget group a long the project time? How Engaging Farmers in Online Forums? How do you work effectively as a TN consortium?
5 min	Closure

Networking included the following participant types:

³¹ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
<input type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)	2	NEFERTITI EURAKNOS
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research	2	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers	4	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)	1	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training	1	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

Networking event number 67

Online event: IDELE internal meeting: presentation of EURAKNOS: which insights for the TNs?

Date: 18/12/2020

Location: Online

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): EURAKNOS (IDELE) / EUROSHEEP (the coordinator, a colleague of IDELE and one other colleague) / Resilience for Dairy : R4D, a new TN that will start in January 2021 (3 colleagues of IDELE, members of the coordination team)

Number of participants in total: 6

Type of networking event³²: internal network of TNs

Highlights: The aims of the meeting were to:

- Make known the EURAKNOS project to a new TN R4D
- To exchange some tips and tricks to manage a European project
- Present the EURAKNOS productions: mainly the Explorer's guide but also the e-knowledge platform
- Try to provide solutions to main issues of the TNs
- To promote the final conference of EURAKNOS that will take place end of next February

³² Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)	6	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)	6	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): It was an internal cross-exchange meeting, so no pictures are available but a specific powerpoint presentation was done and shared with all the participants.

Networking event number 68

The piumbria.com e-platform to strengthen the regional system of knowledge and innovation in the agricultural field (AKIS) and face the challenges of the Farm to Fork strategy

Date: 17/12-2020

Location: Online event

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): From the side of EURAKNOS, the project was represented by Pieter Spanoghe (UGent). There is no information about the whole list of the conference participants.

Number of participants: n.a.

Types of participants: Advisors, policy makers, researchers

Highlights: European Green Deal indicates how to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050 by defining a new sustainable and inclusive growth strategy to stimulate the economy, improve people's health and quality of life and take care of the nature of which humankind is part. The Farm to fork strategy, the heart of the Green Deal, addresses the challenges posed by achieving sustainable food systems in a global way, recognizing the inseparable link between healthy people, healthy societies and a healthy planet. The strategy also represents a central element of the Commission's agenda for achieving the 17 United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (Agenda 2030). All citizens and actors across all value chains, in the EU and elsewhere, should benefit from a transition to sustainability, particularly following the Covid-19 pandemic and economic recession. The transition to a sustainable food system can bring environmental, health, social benefits and guarantee economic benefits for operators. The Farm to fork strategy is a new global approach to the value that Europeans place on food sustainability and represents an opportunity to improve lifestyles, health and the environment. In this context, it is clear that the exchange of knowledge and the diffusion of innovation constitute a transversal objective of the new Community Agricultural Policy. The Commission's communication on the post-2020 CAP "The future of food and agriculture" reiterated the opportunity to strengthen partnerships between advisory services, researchers, national rural networks and farmers' organizations that, taken together, they form Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS).

Networking included:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
<input type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

There is no information about the number of participants per each of the above selected attendee categories.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

Networking event number 69

SCAR SWG AKIS 5th Mandate – 5th Meeting

Date: 20/1-2021

Location: Online event

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): From the side of EURAKNOS, Rosa Mosquera (USC) presented the USC work in the EUREKA project, with references to EURAKNOS. Pieter Spanoghe and Sylvia Burssens (UGent) were present at this meeting and made interventions for EUREKA and EURAKNOS in the chat box (link to education). Other participants Lisa Van Dijck (RAU) Mark Redan, Peter Parea (both involved in EUREKA)

Number of participants: 75

Types of participants: advisory services, FAO, researchers, academics, policymakers national, regional and local level

Highlights: The role of education and training in the EU AKIS:

- Presentation of case studies and H2020 project related to the links between education and AKIS
- How to mobilize the Erasmus+ program?
- Situation and priorities in the member states

One of the aims of SCAR AKIS group is to help member states with the planning and implementation process of their AKIS related activities. One of the topics accepted in our 5th mandate is to emphasize the role of education and training in the AKIS. **At this meeting we propose to highlight the educational and training dimension of AKIS strategy and action plans, taking into account the full range of experiences in the different Member States.** We would like to learn from and discuss the situation and priorities of the MSs and illustrate those discussions with selected case studies. We would also like to explore the possibilities to mobilize the Erasmus+ program to strengthen the educational dimension of the AKIS.

Networking included:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees	Comments
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

There is no information about the number of participants per each of the above selected attendee categories.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

Networking event number 70

Online event: kick-off meeting of R4D (Resilience for Dairy) TN

Date: 29/01/2021

Location: Online

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): all the partners involved in the new TN R4D

Number of participants in total: 45

Type of networking event³³: kick-off meeting of a new TN

Agenda: A 15 minutes presentation for Euraknos. We need to focus on: what is it about? How can it help us for our TN? And where to find more information. Of course, the explorer's guide is very important and we can circulate it during the meeting or show where it can be downloaded.

³³ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

A picture of the all group of participants.

Do you know EURAKNOS project?

Mentimeter

27

In introduction a mentimeter poll was done

A specific powerpoint presentation was done and shared with all the participants.

Networking event number 71

Raiders of the potentially lost Agricultural Knowledge – Presentation of the Key outputs of EURAKNOS

Date: 5/2-2021

Location: Online event hosted by AU/ICROFS (DK)

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): EURAKNOS partners: UGent, PSKW, IDELE, RAU, Ifa, ARC, ACTA, USC, IFOAM Organics Europe, NAK, AUA, AU (ICROFS). EUREKA partners, Members of the KIP.

Number of participants: 150 in total – it was not possible to distinguish between how many participated in the three sessions carried out, respectively.

Types of networking event: Online webinar

Highlights: The Webinar focused on the presentation of the Key output of the EURAKNOS project and started with an overall presentation of the EURAKNOS project.

Then the webinar consisted of three sessions:

1. Explorers guide
2. Policy Brief
3. Digital Platform

After each session, participants engaged in discussions.

Networking included the following participant types: We had a list of participants from the Eventbrite but it is not possible to distinguish between the different groups of participants, as they did not have to indicate their adherence when signing up for the event.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title):

Indicates the start of the first session related to the presentation of the Explorers Guide.

Indicates the start of the second session related to presentation of the Policy Brief.

Indicates the start of the second session related to the presentation of the digital platform.

Networking event number 72

Fostering adaptation of best practices (CEV)

Date: 23/11-2020

Location: Online event, hosted by NAK (Hungary)

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): External partners: 3

Number of participants: ministry, research institute, universities, associations, advisers, farmers, organisers (facilitators)

Types of networking event: CEV

Highlights: n.a.

Networking included the following participant types: n.a.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

Networking event number 73

Chatalytic factors to enhance adaptation of agroforestry (CEV)

Date: 16/12-2020

Location: Online event, hosted by NAK (Hungary)

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): External partners: 2

Number of participants: ministry, research institute, universities, associations, advisers, farmers, organisers (facilitators)

Types of networking event: CEV

Highlights: n.a.

Networking included the following participant types: n.a.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

Networking event number 74

19th NRN Meeting

Date: 11/02/2021

Location: NRNs' online meeting

https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/news-events/events/19th-nrn-meeting_en

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): ENRD Contact point representatives; Inge Van Oost, policy officer at the European Commission, Directorate General Agriculture and Rural Development (DG AGRI); EU National Rural Networks representative.

Number of participants in total: 30 participants

Type of networking event¹: CEV: NRNs' meeting/workshop

Highlights: NRN Estonia (ARC) have made a presentation on concrete topic “Transnational cooperation in EIP-AGRI.” We introduced our state of play in terms of stimulating cross-border cooperation between EU EIP-AGRI operational groups. We took out some important activities between Nordic-Baltic NRNs and have introduced both EURAKNOS and EUREKA projects, as our participation is strongly related to our every-day work and connections with EU partners. Presentation is available here:

https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/sites/enrd/files/2-nrn19_ee-eip_agri_cooperation_r.lambur.pdf

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
<input type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
•	National Rural Networks	25	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		

<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify) ENRD Contact Point and DG AGRI	5	

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title):

19th NRN meeting – Opening session

Connection with Horizon 2020

EURAKNOS
2019-2020

EUREKA
2020-2021

Both projects are developing easily searchable and open source e-platform based on Multi-actor projects results that is available long-term to a broad range of relevant users.

Knowledge reservoir is not just a digital platform, but a tool for people to interact online or directly, offers many opportunities for learning and sharing experiences.

www.euraknos.eu

www.h2020eureka.eu

EUROOPA PROJEKTID

Tava projekti rahastatakse siin:

- Ministeeriumid ja institutsioonid
- Tegevus ja rahastamine
- Partnerid
- Rahastajate poolt
- Agri-Interreg
- Agri-Interreg
- Agri-Interreg

Reve Lambur

Presentation of NRN Estonia.

Networking event number 75

FINAL EURAKNOS CONFERENCE

Date: 26/02-2021

Location: Online, hosted by RAU (UK)

Participants involved (names of organisations represented):

Number of participants in total: In total 109 participants during the entire conference: EURAKNOS partners (RAU, ifa, AUA, PSKW, ACTA, IDELE, NAK, UGent, USC, AU/ICROFS, ARC, LFG, IFOAM-EU), KIP and SIB members. It was not possible to identify organizations represented as participants did not have to state this when signing up for the event. At the start of each of the three sessions in the conference, a Mentimeter was carried in order to identify participants type. The result of the first mentimeter showed that participants was within the following groups: Farmer, forester or other primary producer (7%), Advisory organization, farmers association etc. (14%), Industry, private c company, SME (7%), Policy maker, funding body, government body etc. (5%), University, researcher, Academic (25%), Teacher (3%), Student (2%), Umbrella organization, NGO etc. (7%), Other (3%)

Type of networking event³⁴: EURAKNOS final conference

Highlights: The conference day centered around the handing over the knowledge from EURAKNOS to EUREKA and was divided into three sessions. The first session was targeted towards a general audience showing that EURAKNOS findings can be applied within different areas. This included an interactive round discussion the knowledge platform and MA approach and their relevance to various contexts. The second session focused on how EURAKNOS results can be used by AKIS and the European project community. The presentations focused on the use of the Explorer's Guide and the Platform, which is being further developed in EUREKA. The session was followed by 15 minutes of Q&A. The final session addressed how policy and funding structure can be adapted in order to better support the function and sustainability of TN's to achieve maximal impact. Right after an interactive discussion focused on the long-term vision of knowledge reservoirs in the EU promoting the visibility of TNs and their results and potential national and EU level solutions. The interactive session was joined by Inge Van Oost (policy officer at the European Commission (DG AGRI)), Peter Paree (representing a Dutch farmers association), Matej Stepec from Slovenia (representative of the national government who has worked a lot with rural development), and Kjell Ivarsson (working with agricultural research and Swedish advisory service, a member of the COPA-COCEG) and they acted as external experts/panel members.

³⁴ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

EURAKNOS

FINAL CONFERENCE

From EURAKNOS to the EUREKA of Knowledge Exchange

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863.

Start slide from final conference.

What is your daily work background?

Mentimeter results first session: Asking participants about their background (49 replies).

Where do you come from?

Mentimeter results first session: Asking participants about where they come from (43 replies).

Have you been involved in the EURAKNOS work previously?

Mentimeter results first session: asking participants about previous involvement in the EURAKNOS project (45 replies).

Networking event number 76

Final Panacea Event

Date: 22/2-2021

Location: Online event

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): From the side of EURAKNOS, the projects (both EURAKNOS and EUREKA) were represented by Pieter Spanoghe (UGent).

Number of participants: approximately: 40

Types of participants: Researchers, Advisors, Policy makers, farmers associations, TNs members, Focus Group members.

Highlights: EURAKNOS and EUREKA were presented. Focus on how we are building the digital platform, its use and how users can benefit from it. One of the main outcomes of EURAKNOS were also presented: the explorer's guide.

7. Are you aware of EURAKNOS and EUREKA Network?

8. Are you going to further explore EUREKA and EURAKNOS?

Networking included: n.a.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

UNDERSTANDING *P. CRYPTOGEA* IN YOUR HYDROPONIC SYSTEM

Date: 8/12-2020

Location: PSKW (Online Teams event)

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): From the side of EURAKNOS, the project was represented by PSKW and Els Berckmoes. Alexander Opdebeeck and Robby Sallaets took care of the technical support of the session. PSKW research: Thibault De Moor PSKW advisory services: Isabel Vandevelde – Ilse Leenknecht, Farmers: Madestein (UK), Pure Green Farms (UK), Domarco bvba (Be), Liiuuu, Jepco Glebe, Soiless Systems, De glastuin BV (Be), Ostrowit (Pl), Slamotra (Be), Lv Vyt Van De Vyver (Be)

Number of participants in total: 16

Type of networking event¹: Cross exchange visit - CEV (virtual)

Highlights:

This first session in a series of two, aimed supporting hydroponic lettuce growers to get in contact with each other, advisors and researchers to exchange their latest insights and practical experiences in the field of integrated management of *Phytophthora cryptogea*. During the introduction, the Euraknos project objectives were explained. After this short introduction, a tour the table was performed assuring the participants could get to know each of the participants a bit better. In the interactive session “Understanding *P. cryptogea* in your hydroponic system” Els Berckmoes made a translation of the more scientific findings found in literature to the practical conditions of the farmers’ growing systems. By using Mentimeter, farmers were asked for their opinion, findings, during the presentation, which led to a very interactive session fed by the insights of the farmers. Farmers exchanged their experiences in terms of timing and climate conditions regarding *P. cryptogea* outbreaks. Also, their view on the role of different parameters such as oxygen and temperature was discussed. The presentations input was based on the project outcomes of the Interreg project Recupa which is a research and demonstration project building directly on the outcomes and insights gained from the FERTINNOWA thematic network.

Figure 1 One of the interactive questions answered by the farmers leading to discussion on the impact of greenhouse climate conditions on *P. cryptogea* outbreaks.

Figure 2 Another question leading to quit some discussion on the timing of the visibility of the first disease symptoms

During the second presentation, researcher Thibault de Moor explained the importance of the selection of varieties and the use of chemical treatments to prevent or treat *P. cryptogea* outbreaks.

In a final interactive session, participants were asked about the remaining needs for information on this topic and how they prefer to search or be informed about these topics, making again the link towards the Euraknos initiative.

Networking included the following participant types: n.a.

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title): n.a.

INTEGRATED MANAGEMENT OF *P. CRYPTOGEA*... WHICH TOOLS DO WE HAVE?

Date: 10/12-2020

Location: PSKW (Online event, Teams)

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): From the side of EURAKNOS, the project was represented by PSKW and Els Berckmoes. Alexander Opdebeek and Robby Sallaets took care of the technical support of the session. Other participants: PSKW research: Thibault De Moor, University of Worcester: Tim Pettitt, PSKW advisory services: Isabel Vandevelde – Ilse Leenknecht, Farmers: Madestein (UK), Pure Green Farms (UK) Domarco bvba (Be), Liiuuu (??), Jepco Glebe (??), Soiless Systems, De glastuin BV (Be), Ostrowit (Pl), Slamotra (Be), Lv Vyt Van De Vyver (Be), De Glastuin (Be)

Number of participants in total: 19 (Including Els and guest speakers)

Type of networking event¹: CEV

Highlights: Isabel Vandevelde is a well-known advisor in the field of hydroponic production of lettuce. She guides hydroponic growers in Europe and beyond. During the first presentation, Isabel gave an overview of the history of the *P. cryptogea* problem experienced at the different farms she has been visiting over the past years and explained some main factors. During the second session, Els Berckmoes explained in more detail practical and technical solutions to reduce *P. cryptogea* impact. Researcher Tim Pettitt joined the session and shared his experiences in the field of baiting methods for *P. cryptogea* based on rhododendron leaves. Els Berckmoes explained the beneficial impact of oxygen and systemic disinfection technologies. At the end of the session, farmers were asked again about the remaining information needs. Farmers were unanimous that they liked this type of initiative very much and would like this initiative to be repeated in future.

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
<input type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
X	Operational group	3	Operational group submitted in oct. 2020
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
X	Academic, University & Research	1	

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician	2	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers	9	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)	4	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs Towards A European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

EURAKNOS

UNDERSTANDING *P. CRYPTOGEA* IN HYDROPONIC SYSTEMS...
...IDENTIFYING CHALLENGES AND FIRST APPROACH TOWARDS SOLUTIONS

● An initiative of the H2020 Euraknos project

For the past years, Phytophthora cryptogea has been identified as one of the major challenges faced by producers of hydroponically grown lettuce. Farmers, advisors, technology providers, and researchers have gained insights into this waterborne pathogen.

*Within two interactive sessions, we will present an overview of the current status of insights gained regarding *P. cryptogea*. Both sessions will be organized by use of the online platform Microsoft Teams and last for 60 to 90 minutes.*

<p>SESSION 1: UNDERSTANDING <i>P. CRYPTOGEA</i> IN YOUR HYDROPONIC SYSTEM</p> <p>Content: In this session we integrate most recent scientific insights and translate them into the "hydroponic greenhouse conditions" of mobile gully systems and floating systems</p> <p>This session will learn you more about the life cycle of <i>P. cryptogea</i> and how the reproduction of the pathogen is affected by the present climate conditions of the greenhouse.</p> <p>AGENDA:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Welcome & introduction to the Euraknos project (Els Berckmoes – 5 minutes) - Tour de table (5 minutes) - Understanding <i>P. cryptogea</i> in your hydroponic system (Els Berckmoes – Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt – 15 minutes) - What is the role of oxygen, temperature, nutrients, ... on the development of <i>P. cryptogea</i>? (Anne van Zon – Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt – 15 minutes) - The importance of variety selection and use of chemical treatments (Thibault De Moor – Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt – 10 minutes) - Question and answers session (15 minutes) <p>Interactive round moderated by Els Berckmoes :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are your knowledge needs regarding <i>P. cryptogea</i>? - What are the knowledge gaps? - How can we support you finding the information you need? <p style="text-align: center;">When: 8 December 2020 from 16h00-17h30</p>	<p>SESSION 2: INTEGRATED MANAGEMENT OF <i>P. CRYPTOGEA</i> ... WHICH TOOLS DO WE HAVE?</p> <p>Content: In this session we take a closer look at the different practices and technologies currently available supporting the different aspects of integrated management of <i>P. cryptogea</i> in hydroponic lettuce systems.</p> <p>AGENDA:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Welcome and introduction (Els Berckmoes – 5 minutes) - Tour de table (5 minutes) - Experiences from the hydroponic sector all over Europe (Ilse Leening/Isabel Vandevelde – Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt – 10 minutes) - The additional benefits of hyperoxia conditions in hydroponic systems (speaker to be confirmed – 10 minutes) - Early detection of <i>P. cryptogea</i> (speaker to be confirmed – 10 minutes) - System wide disinfection versus point disinfection (Els Berckmoes – Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt – 10 minutes) <p>Interactive round moderated by Els Berckmoes :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are your knowledge needs regarding <i>P. cryptogea</i> management technologies? What are the knowledge gaps? - How can we support you finding the information you need? <p style="text-align: center;">When: 10 December 2020 from 16h00-17h30</p>
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How can you participate?
 Participation to one/or both sessions is free but registration is required. Once registered you will be provided with a link to the Teams meeting.
Register here: [PROEFSTATION.BEWEBINAREURAKNOS](https://proefstation.be/webinareuraknos)

EURAKNOS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863

Figure 1 Invitation of the CEV *P. cryptogea* 8 & 10 December 2020.

Figure 2 Colleagues of the PSKW research centre during the Euraknos CEV.

Figure 3 Impression of the Euraknos CEV event on the 10th of December.

EURAKNOS

UNDERSTANDING *P. CRYPTOGEA* IN HYDROPONIC SYSTEMS...

...IDENTIFYING CHALLENGES AND FIRST APPROACH TOWARDS SOLUTIONS

● An initiative of the H2020 Euraknos project

For the past years, *Phytophthora cryptogea* has been identified as one of the major challenges faced by producers of hydroponically grown lettuce. Farmers, advisors, technology providers, and researchers have gained insights into this waterborne pathogen.

Within two interactive sessions, we will present an overview of the current status of insights gained regarding *P. cryptogea*. Both sessions will be organized by use of the online platform Microsoft Teams and last for 60 to 90 minutes.

SESSION 1: UNDERSTANDING *P. CRYPTOGEA* IN YOUR HYDROPONIC SYSTEM

Content: In this session we integrate most recent scientific insights and translate them into the "hydroponic greenhouse conditions" of mobile gully systems and floating systems

This session will learn you more about the life cycle of *P. cryptogea* and how the reproduction of the pathogen is affected by the present climate conditions of the greenhouse.

AGENDA:

- Welcome & introduction to the Euraknos project (Els Berckmoes – 5 minutes)
 - Tour de table (5 minutes)
 - Understanding *P. cryptogea* in your hydroponic system (Els Berckmoes – Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt – 15 minutes)
 - What is the role of oxygen, temperature, nutrients, on the development of *P. cryptogea*? (Anne van Zon – Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt – 15 minutes)
 - The importance of variety selection and use of chemical treatments (Thibault De Moor – Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt – 10 minutes)
 - Question and answers session (15 minutes)
- Interactive round moderated by Els Berckmoes:
- What are your knowledge needs regarding *P. cryptogea*?
 - What are the knowledge gaps?
 - How can we support you finding the information you need?

When: 8 December 2020 from 16h00-17h30

SESSION 2: INTEGRATED MANAGEMENT OF *P. CRYPTOGEA*.... WHICH TOOLS DO WE HAVE?

Content: In this session we take a closer look at the different practices and technologies currently available supporting the different aspects of integrated management of *P. cryptogea* in hydroponic lettuce systems.

AGENDA:

- Welcome and introduction (Els Berckmoes – 5 minutes)
 - Tour de table (5 minutes)
 - Experiences from the hydroponic sector all over Europe (Iise Leenknecht/Isabel Vandevelde – Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt – 10 minutes)
 - The additional benefits of hyperoxia conditions in hydroponic systems (speaker to be confirmed – 10 minutes)
 - Early detection of *P. cryptogea* (speaker to be confirmed – 10 minutes)
 - System wide disinfection versus point disinfection (Els Berckmoes – Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt – 10 minutes)
- Interactive round moderated by Els Berckmoes:
- What are your knowledge needs regarding *P. cryptogea* management technologies? What are the knowledge gaps?
 - How can we support you finding the information you need?

When: 10 December 2020 from 16h00-17h30

How can you participate?

Participation to one/or both sessions is free but registration is required.

Once registered you will be provided with a link to the Teams meeting.

Register here: [PROEFSTATION.BE/WEBINAREURAKNOS](https://proefstation.be/webinareuraknos)

EURAKNOS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863

The EURAKNOS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No: 817863

Mobilizing Networks

Date: 22-09/2020

Location: Online, hosted by RAU (UK)

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): RAU, Farming Connect, IFA, Ugent University, NAK, Exeter University, CCRI, ADAS, FIBL, IDELE, ZLTO, ICROFS, LHWF, Aberystwyth University, Prolinnova

Number of participants in total: 23

Type of networking event³⁵:

CEV (online) Mobilizing networks

Highlights: Cross exchange network activity report

Compiled by Jessica Stokes: On Tuesday 22nd September 2020, the RAU hosted a EURAKNOS and Farmer Led Innovation Network (FLIN) cross exchange webinar on Mobilizing Networks, hosted by Dr Jessica Elizabeth Stokes, and Dr Lisa Williams van Dijk via zoom, starting at 12pm and lasting 1.5 hours. The event was promoted via an Eventbrite page, and published on both the EURAKNOS and FLIN twitter accounts. In total, 30 people signed up to attend, of which 23 people attended on the day. These attendees range from researchers, facilitators, consultants, farmers, environmentalists, and project managers joined us from across the UK, Amsterdam, France, The Netherlands, Scotland, and Denmark (for full details see screen shots below).

³⁵ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

Who is here? Please type your name, where you are in the world, and describe yourself in a few words...

Mentimeter

Jess, Bristol (UK). Researcher, facilitator and organic veg grower!

Lynfa Davies, Aberystwyth UK Knowledge Exchange Manager for Farming Connect

Laura Palczynski, Shropshire UK, researcher at Innovation for Agriculture and collaborator on EU projects DISARM and EURAKNOS

Aniko rural development expert from NAK

David. Scotland. Work for an environmental NGO.

Tyler Arbour, American in Belgium, EUREKA project

Ilse A Rasmussen, Denmark, worked with organic agriculture for more than 40 years, mainly research, now administration

Beth, Exeter (South West England) and I'm finishing up my PhD, I'm an agricultural and environmental lawyer, mediator, facilitator :-)

Julie Ingram. Researcher from UK

22

Who is here? Please type your name, where you are in the world, and describe yourself in a few words...

Mentimeter

Alistair Prior, Falkirk, Scotland Rural Policy Bod

Sarah Kendall, Nottinghamshire, ADAS Research Scientist with an interest in on-farm innovation and networks

Thomas Alföldi FiBL Switzerland Dissemination and communication video

Daniel Kindred, Crop researcher, ADAS, UK ... switching between webinars so only half here!

Malene, Denmark, academic/admin staff at International Centre for Research in Organic Food Systems. Have worked with organic farming since 80'ties

Maxime Marois, France (Eastern South) IDELE

Paula Baker Laying Hen Welfare Forum (Not so sunny Somerset) Fun, passionate researcher

Eelke Wielinga, Dutch consultant at ZLTO

Lisa, Bristol, UK, vet and lover of farmer led innovation!

22

The cross exchange event was facilitated by Lisa Williams van Dijk and Jessica Elizabeth Stokes (RAU), who welcomed everyone and familiarized the group with the agenda and rules of engagement.

EURAKNOS & FLIN webinar series

Mobilising networks

- Welcome and thank you for joining us today.
- While waiting, please familiar yourself with the following:
- **Chat:** feel free to share comments and thoughts with the other participants. During the webinar you can also submit questions to us using the chat function.
- Your hosts today are Lisa Williams van Dijk and Jessica Stokes
- We are looking forward to getting started in a few minutes

Lisa then introduced everyone to the objectives and the format of the cross exchange webinar, and promoted the EURAKNOS project, its role in relation to mobilizing networks, and the ultimate outcome of creating a farm book of knowledge:

- 2 year multi-actor H2020 project
- Strengthening the EU agriculture knowledge base by making the knowledge from H2020 projects more accessible to farming and rural communities.
- Bringing all content together and creating one single web platform-> e-knowledge reservoir.
- Sister project EUREKA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863.

The cross exchange webinar then received a dynamic and illuminating key note speech from Dr Eelke Wielinga. Since his PhD on Networks as Living Tissue, Dr Eelke Wielinga has been a key driving force behind the language, tools and energy for networkers, stimulating innovations via networks in the Dutch agricultural sector and European Innovation Partnership program (EIP). For example Eelke was a consultant on the AgriSpin project on Innovation Support Agencies, bringing 15 partner organisations from 12 European countries together to learn and inspire each other in ways to support innovating farmers. In this key note talk, Eelke shared insights into how networkers mobilise to optimise network health, energy and function.

Keynote – Dr Eelke Wielinga

The webinar then moved into a panel discussion, where Eelke was joined by Alistair Prior, a Scottish policy representative who designed and put in place the Rural Innovation Support Service as part of his role as Head of the Scottish Rural Network Support Unit in the Scottish Government, working closely with colleagues across Scotland, UK and EU on rural development policy and innovation support for much of the last 10 years. Also on the panel was David Michie, Soil Association Scotland's Associate Director of Farming and Land Use. David directs policy, public affairs, and programme activities to support, enable, and connect land managers in Scotland to work with nature to build thriving, resilient businesses. He shared his main interest which is in systems based approaches to sustainable food production. Dr Laura Palczynski, a researcher in the Livestock department at Innovation for Agriculture, an agricultural knowledge exchange charity was also on the panel. Laura has been involved in several European thematic networks, namely 4d4f, DISARM and EURAKNOS. Laura shared her insights around communication and dissemination within networks.

Panel discussion

The final part of the cross exchange webinar was facilitated by an interactive session with networking participants. This gave participants an opportunity to share ideas and generate new ones. This session highlighted new opportunities that have emerged for mobilising networks in the era of COVID, such as the benefits of online tools to facilitate engagement and cross border networks, reach a wider diversity of participants, such as those in more remote areas who struggle to travel to face to face events.

Before we closed the webinar, we asked participants for their feedback to establish to what extent our objectives of the networking event had been met. Please see the full results completed by 14 participants below:

We also asked for further comments on how to improve. These were particularly useful given this was the first cross exchange webinar series we had delivered online. Here we received both positive feedback on the usefulness of networking exchange, as well as new ideas for future events, and the farm book, such as everyone bringing a colleague to networking events like this who are new to the subject, and the request for an online forum to pose questions and share new ideas on how to facilitate networks:

The full cross exchange webinar was recorded. These can be found by following the links below.

The full webinar is available on you tube here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9o-OVgv6Apl>

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
<input type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks	4	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research	11	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician	4	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		

<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers	1	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media	1	
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO	1	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor	1	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Mobilising networks

To optimise network health, energy and function

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs Towards A European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

The EURAKNOS project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No: 817863

Networking event number 80

Facilitating farmer led innovation

Date: 17/09/2020

Location: Online, hosted by RAU (UK)

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): AHDB, KTN, IfA, ORC, ADAS, University of York, Cumbria Wildlife Trust, LHWF, RAU, CSF, SLU, Ugent University, Pukka Herbs UK, Soil Association

Number of participants in total: 30

Type of networking event³⁶: CEV (online) Facilitating Farmer Led Innovation

Highlights: Cross exchange network activity report

Compiled by Jessica Stokes On Thursday 17th September 2020, the RAU hosted a EURAKNOS and Farmer Led Innovation Network (FLIN) cross exchange webinar on Facilitating Farmer Led Innovation, hosted by Dr Lisa Williams van Dijk via zoom, starting at 11am and lasting 1.5 hours. The event was promoted via an Eventbrite page, and published on both the EURAKNOS and FLIN twitter accounts. In total, 100 people signed up to attend, however 30 people attended on the day. These attendees range from researchers, industry reps, journalists, facilitators, advisors, welfare organisations, farmers, vets, environmentalists, project managers joined us from across the UK, Europe and even Australia (for full details see screen shots below).

³⁶ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

Who is here? Please type your name, where you are and describe yourself in three words. Mentimeter

Luke Harmer, AHDB, Digital Skills Manager	Lisa Morgans, Bristol, Enthusiastic, curious, chatty	Genevieve Metson, Linköping Sweden, scientist nutrient enthusiast
Farm/farmer researcher	Lucy Mather, KTN, Livestock Knowledge Transfer Manager	Lynfa Davies, Aberystwyth Knowledge Exchange manager
Charlotte Bickler, Organic Research Centre, Knowledge Exchange Manager	Im Carlos Ayala, Project Manager for the FARMS-SAFE AMR Project in Argentina led in the UK by the University of Bristol	Russ Herefordshire Cows Regenerative Mentor

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Who is here? Please type your name, where you are and describe yourself in three words. Mentimeter

Helen Brookes, AHDB,	Jonathan Ensor, University of York, Social Learning Researcher	Maria Gernert, Brussels, curious, creative & caring
Kat Wolton, ADAS, Agri business consultant	Christa Nelson, Cumbria Wildlife Trust, grassland conservation officer	Sarah Kendall, ADAS, in Nottinghamshire Intrigued, Passionate, Determined
Tim Messeder from the KTN based in Leicester in the U.K.	Judith Tooth, Suffolk, freelance journalist and photographer	Caroline Hanks Herefordshire facilitator meadows transformation

29

Who is here? Please type your name, where you are and describe yourself in three words. Mentimeter

PAULA BAKER, LAYING HEN WELFARE FORUM (PRO)	Gabriela Olmos (SLU, Sweden) - Researcher interested in understanding Farmer/Owner - Vet interactions	Isabel Ross (Griffiths), Pukka Herbs UK, organic fair farming
Jess, bristol, researcher, facilitator, activist.	Phillippa Griffiths, Shropshire, UK. Interested, realist, agriculture	Jemima. London. Vet, environmental interest.
Rachel.MonmouthshireCSF, farming, advice	Kate Still Soil Association Farming advisor, project manager	Tyler Arbour, Ghent Belgium, (geo)microbiologist, aspiring soil/agriculture professional...

29

The cross exchange event was facilitated by Lisa Williams van Dijk, who welcomed everyone and familiarised the group with the agenda and rules of engagement.

EURAKNOS & FLIN webinar series

Facilitating Farmer-led Innovation

- Welcome and thank you for joining us today.
- While waiting, please familiar yourself with the following:
 - **Chat:** feel free to share comments and thoughts with the other participants. During the webinar you can also submit questions to us using the chat function.
 - Your host today is Lisa Williams van Dijk
- We are looking forward to getting started in a few minutes

Lisa then introduced everyone to the objectives and the format of the cross exchange webinar, and promoted the EURAKNOS project, its role in relation to facilitating farmer led innovation, and the ultimate outcome of creating a farm book of knowledge:

- 2 year multi-actor H2020 project
- Strengthening the EU agriculture knowledge base by making the knowledge from H2020 projects more accessible to farming and rural communities.
- Bringing all content together and creating one single web platform-> e-knowledge reservoir.
- Sister project EUREKA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863.

The cross exchange webinar then show cased tools and tips for facilitating farmer led innovation, online and in the field. Our keynote speaker was Russ Carrington, former general manager at the Pasture-Fed Livestock Association (PFLA), a grass roots, farmer led movement practicing, advocating and certifying over 600 regenerative farmers in the UK. Russ highlighted his and the PFLA’s change journey which facilitated regenerative agriculture innovation, and the benefits of an online forum to compliment facilitation in the field, creating and reinforcing a culture which fosters an inclusive community of practice, building trust between members and enabling collaborative knowledge exchange.

The webinar then moved into a panel discussion, where Russ was joined by Kate Still (Farming Programme Delivery Manager at Soil Association), Dr Lisa Morgans (Head of Precision Livestock at

Innovation for Agriculture) and Dr Jessica Stokes (facilitator on Hennovation and farm animal welfare and policy lecturer at RAU) to share tips, tools and reflections of facilitating farmer led innovation in the field.

Panel discussion

In particular, the process and qualities of facilitation were reflected upon, for example the importance of facilitator as the antenna of the group, continually assessing, monitoring and reflecting on where the community are on their individual and collective innovation journey; being flexible and adaptive to changing needs, energy and aspirations.

The final part of the cross exchange webinar was facilitated by an interactive session with networking participants. This gave participants an opportunity to share ideas and generate new ones. This session highlighted new opportunities that have emerged for facilitating farmer led innovation in the era of COVID, such as the rise of virtual interactive farm tours, zoom webinars

and meetings, flipped labs/classrooms, and the rise of the use of WhatsApp and podcasts to create communities of practice and share farmer led innovation.

Before we closed the webinar, we asked participants for their feedback to establish to what extent our objectives of the networking event had been met. Please see the full results completed by 16 participants below:

We also asked for further comments on how to improve. These were particularly useful given this was the first cross exchange webinar we had delivered online. It is important to note that although

we included some interaction between participants, we would benefit from allocating more time to this, and using the breakout room facility:

The full cross exchange webinar was recorded and a follow up podcast was created. These can be found by following the links below:

The full webinar is available on you tube here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QBgazDw-ba0>

A podcast between Dr Jessica Stokes and Russ Carrington showcasing the importance of **facilitating farmer led innovation** (in addressing our multiple food, farming and societal challenges of ecological breakdown, climate change and Brexit) is available here: https://open.spotify.com/episode/4RF5BHgMohSwYjSCRpeF0w?si=jx7bfIO_Tv2y7iqJHJcpqA&nd=1

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
<input type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)	4	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks	1	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research	10	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician	4	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers	3	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media	1	
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO	3	Agriculture, environment and conservation
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)	2	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training	2	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

CEV ON BEST PRACTICES FOR MULTI-ACTOR APPROACHES AND DISSEMINATION STRATEGIES IN THE FIELD ON SMART PROTECTION

Date: 9/7/2020

Location: Online, hosted by UGent (Belgium)

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): Project coordinators of Smart AKIS, SMARTPROTECT, OPTIMA, INNOSETA, IPMWORKS presented and discussed their project. Besides, two Operational Groups (OGs) were invited to present: Smart spraying on Olive Trees and W&W leeks and

Number of participants in total: 21

Type of networking event³⁷: CEV (online)

Highlights: Regarding end-users engagement, foster interactions between actors is a crucial aspect. Peer to peer learning is fundamental, and farmers need to be put in the condition to work with other farmers that are willing to demonstrate technical solutions (by creating hubs of farms, farmers that are not in the network can be involved in demonstration activities). It is the case of OG "Smart spraying on Olive Trees". In fact, in Greece farms are grouped in "cooperatives" that act as role models. If they adopt new technologies or practices the others will follow by themselves, creating an easy environment to disseminate. Fundamentally, peer to peer knowledge exchange happens also between advisors and facilitators through training and sector meetings. They need to build specific skills for coaching and foster the knowledge exchange among actors (technical skills are not enough to create an enabling environment. This was also demonstrated during workshops organized during the EURAKNOS project, where the "ideal" skills that a facilitator should have were defined. One of many is to be able to interact with several groups of people). Furthermore, training and workshops will also allow us to understand end-user needs and to disseminate outside the network and to form advisors outside the project. Farmers need to be involved since the preliminary phases of the project and it would be excellent to create a community of end-users before the start. The TN Smart AKIS worked on this and it also involved media. By involving farmers and end-users since the beginning, it is possible to adjust the originally planned path in favor of their needs. Brochures, questionnaires, and face-

to-face interviews seemed to be an efficient way to collect their input that can be verified by establishing focus groups. End-user can also be involved by creating a platform where they can directly insert materials. It is the case of the Innoseta platform. Once uploaded, the material is verified not only from researchers but also directly by farmers during workshops (at national and

³⁷ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

international levels). Another example of a good end-user engagement from where a series of workshops with 375 participants were organized at the beginning of the project. It was possible to collect participants' needs and their first ideas on the platform. Furthermore, a panel that involved farmers and advisors from 12 countries was set. This allowed us to ask small questions online to organize inputs in the development stage of the platform. Actively involving farmers since the conceptualization phase of the project is fundamental, therefore building an EU network of farmers and advisors remains a challenge. Emilio Gil, the coordinator of Innoseta encourage the involvement of local farmers association because they are directly in contact with farmers and it will be easier to engage them in project activities, hence reinforcing the local network. Another aspect that each project should have since the beginning is a good connection with other projects. OPTIMA project is about to start and it can already count on a good connection with Demofarms project, Agridemo, Nefertiti, Diversifood, AGrilink, and i2connect. This will allow enhancing the impact of the project, involve a wider group of actors and to disseminate to a broader group of end-users. Another challenge is to involve other actors such as consumers and the agri-food chain. This is a gap that is highlighted also in the EURKNOS project. While analyzing 34 TNs, it has been noticed that this category is not involved in the Multi Actor concept. In terms of a good dissemination strategy, unfortunately, there is not a formula that works for every project. Therefore, a good practice is to have clear since the beginning the target groups and stay focused on what is important and interesting for them. Furthermore, according to OG "W&W leeks and cabbages" and the coordinator of the Smart AKIS project, Google analytics helped to target the dissemination since it provides a clear view of what is seen. Lastly, it is important to disseminate at the local level by using the channels that are most popular in a specific country. All the information must be sent in an easy-to-understand language. During this cross-exchange, many interesting points were tackled. First of all, the peer to peer knowledge exchange trough workshops and farm demonstration. These tools allow a fruitful interaction between actors as well as an efficient way to collect critics and input to lead the project in the right direction, addressing the end-users needs as much as possible. Therefore, many challenges need to be faced, in fact more effort need to be spent regarding the involvement of categories of actors such as consumers and the agri-food chain, and building an EU network of farmers and advisors. This will allow to wide projects dissemination and increase their impact.

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
x	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
x	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
x	Academic, University & Research		
x	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Networking event number 82

French national event presenting the EURAKNOS project

Date: 16/3- 2021

Location: online

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): ACTA, IFV, IDELE

Number of participants in total: Around 25

Type of networking event³⁸: National conference

Highlights: Short report of the networking event. Focus on the networking about EURAKNOS – presenting and or discussing about EURAKNOS. Do not report about the event itself if it is not related to EURAKNOS. During the event, we started by a global presentation of the participants' profile and their expectations by attending to this national event. Then, we presented the explorer's guide, its content and how it can be used; the good practices to communicate and disseminate in a thematic network, with reference mainly to deliverable D2.3 and the C&D strategy of EURAKNOS put in place during the project, the website (page of deliverables); the prototype of the platform and the policy brief, highlighting the sixth recommendations made by EURAKNOS. People seemed to be very interested in the project's outputs, many of them concluded that the conference filled their expectations and some of them asked for receiving the guide and the presentations. The representative of the national rural network working at the French ministry for agriculture have been very enthusiastic about EURAKNOS' results and would like to invite us to present those results during a webinar hold by the NRN and EIP-Agri in June 2021.

Here is the link to the video: <https://youtu.be/QUU4gdiH184>

³⁸ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
x	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)	4	
x	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)	1	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
x	Academic, University & Research	4	
x	Adviser/consultant/technician	3	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
x	Chamber/council of agriculture	2	
x	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry	2	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
x	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)	9	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Presentation of the Explorer's Guide

Evenement France EURAKNOS 16/03/21

Une des productions emblématiques : le guide de l'explorateur

- En préambule, quelques définitions
 - Que sont les réseaux thématiques (RT) ?
- 2 objectifs principaux :
 - Mettre en relation des communautés de chercheurs et de praticiens de terrain afin de faciliter et d'augmenter la diffusion de connaissances scientifiques.
 - Traduire ces connaissances en sources d'informations facilement compréhensibles par l'utilisateur final sous des formes variées «résumés des pratiques utiles», des brochures, des supports audiovisuel : photos, vidéos, podcasts...).

→ Volonté de produire, diffuser et conserver
⇒ cibler les bons canaux de diffusion et trouver des solutions durables d'hébergement des contenus.

Résultats du projet EURAKNOS – événement France – 16/03/2021

Presentation of the Policy Brief

Evenement France EURAKNOS 16/03/21

Le policy brief

A qui est-il destiné ?

- Aux décideurs pour faire évoluer les idées ou aider à la décision.
- Acteurs institutionnels, décideurs et négociateurs publics ;
- Décideurs privés, entreprises, associations, organisations non gouvernementales (Ong) ;
- Également les relais d'opinion.

EURAKNOS

Networking event number 83

MAP IoF2020

Date: 18/3-2021

Location: Online

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): IFOAM Organics Europe, Inter-Bio Romania, EIT-Food, Innovation for Agriculture; companies, e.g. Signify, Evonik Industries, Fundie Ventures, CRI Paris, research institutes, e.g. WUR, Aarhus University, TSSG, ATB-Bremen, CTIFL; governmental bodies/public authorities; agricultural cooperatives, e.g. CUMA (France) – presumably many IoF project partners

Number of participants in total: 26

Type of networking event³⁹: Networking activity related to MAP IoF2020

Highlights: Presenting the EURAKNOS project (introduction by IFOAM Organics Europe) and key outputs (Explorer's Guide, Vision Paper, Policy Brief presented by guest Laura Palczynski from IfA); linking to EUREKA, presentation of the platform prototype, end-user involvement and possibilities for connections with multi-actor projects (presented by guest project coordinator Pieter Spanoghe, UGhent)

³⁹ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
X	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)	20-26	Multiple types possible
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
X	International organisations	3	
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
X	Academic, University & Research	7	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
X	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry	4	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
X	Farmers association	3	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
X	NGO	3	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
X	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)	3	
X	Umbrella organisation	3	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Pictures (please add at least 2 pictures + provide pictures title)

Presentation of EURAKNOS & EUREKA at IoF2020 final event

IOF 2020 FINAL EVENT

Speaker: Maria Gernert

EURAKNOS Explorer's Guide

- How to design and implement TNs & other multi-actor projects to maximise user engagement & impact
 - Based on common issues, experiences and concerns of TNs
 - 6 online validation workshops with 40-60 participants

PRE-FUNDING	PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION		POST-FUNDING
CONCEPTUALISATION Finding user engagement through framing of user's demand through external project design SECTION 2 Looks at the MAA, how to build a risk consortium, and approaches strategies for maximising user engagement Multi-actor approach	INITIALISATION Agreeing on how you work together to achieve your project objectives SECTION 3 Provides insights on how to function effectively as a multi-actor network Working effectively as a multi-actor network	EXECUTION Conducting your project activities 1. User need identification 2. Identifying and collecting knowledge 3. Designing and commissioning 4. Implementation SECTION 4 Supports the actual implementation of your TN project activities	POST-EXECUTION Counting user engagement through framing of your consortium and defining project design SECTION 5 Focuses on measuring the sustainability of your TN in terms of health and economics, and on how to measure your impact Measuring impact & sustainability

EURAKNOS

LIVE 04:09 19

IOF 2020 FINAL EVENT

Speaker: Maria Gernert

Understanding the end user

EUREKA → WP2: Understanding the end-user

Why?

There's no chance that the iPhone is going to get any significant market share. No chance.

EURAKNOS

LIVE 20:13 21

Networking event number 84

Online study meeting

Date: 23/03/2021

Location: Online, hosted by UGent (Belgium)

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): UGent

Number of participants in total: 60

Type of networking event⁴⁰: Study meeting for farmers

Highlights: The main outputs of EURAKNOS were presented. Special attention to the platform

⁴⁰ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
<input type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
X	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
X	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Networking event number 85

SWG SCAR AKIS - 5th Meeting

Date: 25/03/2021

Location: Online, hosted by UGent (Belgium)

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): UGent

Number of participants in total: 70

Type of networking event⁴¹: SWG SCAR AKIS - 5th Meeting

Highlights: The main outputs of EURAKNOS were presented. This SCAR SWG AKIS online meeting will be the 5th meeting of the 5th mandate endorsed by the SCAR plenary in December 2018. Its specific role is to **discuss the following topic defined in the 5th mandate:**

1. AKIS policies at national and EU level creating further EIP synergies
2. Achieving greater Impact of the Multi-Actor Approach (MAA) implementation in EU AKISs
3. The role of Education in the EU AKIS

This meeting will develop the following topics:

- COM and MS presentations on education (complement to the previous AKIS meeting on education)
- MS presentations about the status of their CAP AKIS Strategic Plans
- MS discussion on the implementation of experiences of AKIS related measures

⁴¹ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
x	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
x	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
x	Academic, University & Research		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
x	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
x	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
x	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
x	Umbrella organisation		
x	Advisory training		
x	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Networking event number 86

Innovation camp

Date: 23/03/2021

Location: Zoom, hosted by ARC (Estonia)

Website: <https://maainfo.ee/index.php?id=7362&page=3394&>

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): Innovation brokers from: Estonian Life Sciences university, Estonian Crop Research Institute, Farmers Union, Rural Development Foundation, private companies, Ministry of Rural Affairs, Innovation clusters, Leader Local Action Group (Kodukant Läänemaa).

Number of participants in total: 24

Type of networking event⁴²: Online workshop

Highlights: Agenda of 3rd innovation camp

- 1) Throwback to previous Innovation camps (held in 2019 and 2020) and homework
- 2) Presentation and explanation of “Explorers guide to thematic networks” main findings and important aspects: How to design and implement thematic networks, to maximise user engagement and impact.

⁴² Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
<input type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
•	National Rural Networks	5	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
•	Innovation broker	19	That regional event was oriented only for Innovation brokers (for persons who are initiating new projects, creation of new networks-
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

Innovation camp participants

Palju osalisi

MIDA TÄHENDAB MITME OSAPOOLEGA LÄHENEMINE TEMAATILISE VÕRGUSTIKU JAKKS?

MAA põhimõte on teadusest ja praktilisest tegevusest omandatud ainulaadsete ning üksteist täiendavate oskustega inimeste kokkutoimine. Eesmärk on luua koostöös teadmisi, mida põllumajandustootjad või metsamajandajad saaksid konkreetsel teemal oma töös kasutada.

Usalduslike suhete loomine on organisatsioonide ja üksikisikute vahel MA lähenemisviisi edu võti. Kõigi projekti osapoolte koostöö on otsustava tähtsusega, et ühendada neid teadmiste, kogemuste ja vaatenurkade erinevaid allikaid.

Temaatilise võrgustiku eesmärk on luua praktikapõhiseid lahendusi põllumajandustootjate, metsamajandajate ja teiste kasutajate väljakutsetele ning luua ühiselt lahendusi kohalikul, piirkondlikul või üleriigilisel tasandil.

MA lähenemisviisi edu tagab juhendaja (ingl. k. facilitator), kelle roll on suurendada osapoolte panust ja hoida võrgustik dünaamilise, ühiselt õppiva ja loova ökosüsteemina tegevuses. Temaatilises võrgustikus rakendatakse MA lähenemist kahel tasandil.

- 1. Konsortsiumi tasand**, mis hõlmab temaatilise võrgustiku eesmärgi jaoks olulisi osapooli, näiteks nõustamise, teadus-, põllumajandus- ja metsandus-organisatsioone.
- 2. Projekti rakendamise tasand**, kus tegevused tuginevad vahetule koostööle kasutajatega. Eesmärk on luua teadmisi rakendamiseks võrgustikus vahetult seotud kasutajate poolt ning levitamiseks ja kasutamiseks laiemalt.

PRAKTIKAPÕHISED INNOVATSIOONIVÕRGUSTIKUD

Projektipartnerid on leidnud, et mitme osapoollega praktikapõhise innovatsioonivõrgustike edukus sõltub järgnevast:

- oluliste osapoolte aktiivne osalus,
- professionaalne vahendamine (facilitation),
- mõeldukas ressurtsugi
- ligipääs asjakohastele ekspertteadmistele.

MITME HUVRÜHMAGA PARTNERLISE TÖÖ ÜHEND

Tutvuge sellel <http://www.msp.tol.ee>

Selles juhenduses rühmitatud ühenduste eesmärk on:

- Ühine tegevus erinevate osapoolte vahel
- Lahknev selgitage nendega
- Koostöö lahenda osaleda
- Lähene võiksid viimist
- Puhke

Explanation of multi-actor approach

You are viewing Hanna Tamsalu's screen View Options View

Projekti tulemuste rakendamine

- Aktiivne kaasamine juba teadmiste kogumisse
- Valideerimise seminarid
- Võistlused ja konkursid, millega „sundida“ praktikat proovima
- Koolitused ja väljaõpe
 - INCREDIBLE innovatsioonivõistlus ja järelkoolitus
 - AGRIFORVALOR koolitusmaterjalid koolidele
- Tulemuste lõimimine riiklikku poliitikasse, EL määrustesse
- Uute uuringute algatamine

Implementation of project results (from Explorer's guide)

Euroopa teabe vahendamine Eestisse

Bringing European knowledge to Estonian end-users

Networking event number: 87

TNs and online knowledge reservoir, important element of the knowledge transfer puzzle

Date: 22.03.2021.

Location: Online, hosted by NAK (Budapest, Hungary)

Participants involved (names of organisations represented): registered advisers in a high percentage, professors from universities (ELTE, MATE, SZE)

Number of participants in total: 145

Type of networking event⁴³: national final assembly

Highlights: EURAKNOS results and their exploitation possibilities were presented. In terms of exploitation the focus was on the national AKIS system in which universities and advisory system play a crucial role. After presentations there was an interesting panel discussion about enhancing national knowledge exchange network through multi-actor projects and other tools. In the discussion almost the whole national AKIS system was presented. An adviser, a representative of a research institute, a well experienced professor, project manager of other relevant MA projects (who was also the representative of the advocacy body and the national AKIS network) participated in the discussion. Also, a policy maker (representative from the ministry) was supposed to participate but she had to cancel it at the last moment because of another engagement. The different approach (adviser was more business oriented than the other participants) of the invited people came out in a constructive form during the conversation.

Highlights & lessons learned:

1. How knowledge exchange between science and practical life can be enhanced with TN, knowledge reservoir and other tools, and what kind of new possibilities are given by digitalization?
 - a. **Advisers are “the bridge”**, digital tools make it easier this needs IT skills, trust, openness and motivation from both sides.
 - b. It can accelerate the knowledge transfer if advisory body **has an apparatus to collect and simplify** (translate to the farmer’s language) the worldwide released innovation results (Danish example)
 - c. **Sample farm system combined with national and international cross visit programs** was a well-functioning tool (Islandic example, but before it was also available in Hungary)
 - d. Not only the **vertical but also the horizontal connections** can faster the flow of information and projects like EURAKNOS promote networking, sharing of knowledge is recoverable depends a lot on proactive attitude.
2. How a **knowledge reservoir can reach its main aim, a widespread knowledge exchange and what kind of role the central coordination plays in this and in the quality assurance ?**

⁴³ Networking activities related to

- TN, networks of TNs, OGs and MAPs: Joint workshops, bilateral meeting, CEVs etc.
- With similar initiatives or organisations at regional, national, EU & international level: SIB meetings, EIP-AGRI seminars, SWG SCAR AKIS meetings, EUFRAS meeting etc.
- Education and Training: workshops, bilateral meetings/contacts, courses etc.

- a. If a reservoir is widely used, a **community** will be built on (filtered information, reaching each other through chat). **Networking** within the community is **basement for trust of end users and for quality assurance**.
 - b. **Central coordination, reliable and easily understandable, searchable information** is crucial. Also a **“business model”** is crucial (although not everyone agreed on fully). Value proposition of a widely used knowledge reservoir is minimization of innovation risks through information, this should counterbalance lack of time and fear of competition.
 - c. Central coordination’s rule is **multiply knowledge reliable items, facilitating interactions, and helping with digital blockages, ensuring quality assurance** (and also?! drawing up basic payback calculations).
 - d. **Variety of information types is also a tensile force for better exploitation**, for example podcast, infographics, video’s are nice tool to orientate the interest.
 - e. It is very important is to make **this reservoir available for everybody on his/her language and applicable level and to reach this is mainly the task of the national central coordination (or contact point or support body)**.
3. What is outlined in evolving national AKIS strategy?
 - a. Role of **support bodies will be emphasized more** (to translate the innovation result to farmer’s language). Beside this the development of the strategy is happening in a strong cooperation with all actors (also regular workshops for endusers -NAK’s members-).
 - b. **Pilot end users (farmers, advisers) could have more emphasized role in the AKIS network** (Austrian example) and formal and informal networking events can be combined.
 4. How to promote participation in multi-actor projects?
 - a. The key factor is **facilitation, giving competences to self-study and to collaborate**.
 - b. **Best practices (collected on open source platform) encourage** also the participation. According to possibilities descriptions of best practices have to be **complemented with basic payback calculations**
 - c. **Easily understandable informational materials** like Explorer Guide encourage also participation.

Networking included the following participant types:

Tick if applicable	Networking participant types	Number of attendees (approximate)	Comments
<input type="checkbox"/>	H2020 project (TN, MA or other)	4	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Focus group (EIP-AGRI)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Operational group		
<input type="checkbox"/>	International organisations		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks	1	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Academic, University & Research	8	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Adviser/consultant/technician	122	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory association/company	10	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Chamber/council of agriculture		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Enterprises, SME & Larger incl. Industry		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers & foresters, primary producers		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmers association		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Government		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Innovation broker		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Media		
<input type="checkbox"/>	National Rural Networks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	NGO		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Policy maker incl. Political advisor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Research/Technical Centre (& Advisory)		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Umbrella organisation		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Advisory training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Vocational training		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)		

The screenshot shows a Zoom meeting interface. The main window displays a presentation slide titled "EURAKNOS tematikus hálózat rövid bemutatása". The slide contains the following information:

- <https://www.euraknos.eu/>
- Többszereplős (multi-actor) projekt az EIP-Agri H2020 Program keretében
- Célkitűzése a tematikus hálózatok összekapcsolása, módszertani fejlesztése és az egységes európai tudástár alapjainak megerősítése

A diagram on the slide illustrates the process: "Tematikus hálózatok (TN) elemzése" leads to "E-tudástár prototípus kialakítása", which leads to "Meglévő TN-ek hatásának megerősítése". A map of Europe is shown to the right of the diagram.

Below the diagram, the slide lists results:

- **Eredménye:** online tudástár prototípusa, tematikus hálózat módszertani útmutató („Explorer Guide”), szakpolitikai ajánlás
- 16 tagú európai konzorcium, AKI és NAK részvételével
- Testvérprojektje a 21 tagú konzorciummal megvalósuló Eureka, melyben a tudástár prototípusát fejlesztik tovább

The Zoom interface shows a list of participants on the right, including Jakab Erika, Bányai Tamás, Kormondi Sándor, Lukács Márta, Vrancsik László, Hárshgyi Márk, and Tóth Krisztina. The bottom of the screen shows the Windows taskbar with the time 03:37:33.

Presentation about EURAKNOS results

The screenshot shows a Zoom meeting interface during a panel discussion. The main window displays a grid of nine video thumbnails. The participants are:

- Vilgó Szabolcs
- Nagy Anikó
- Vér András
- Nagy László (Guest) (Vendég)
- Liebmann János (Guest) (Vendég)
- Liebmann-né Veres Éva Mária (Guest) (Vendég)
- Gáborné Jakab Ágnes
- Biró Szabolcs
- Alexis Wagner (Agrárszakácsadó)

The Zoom interface shows a list of participants on the right, including Vér András, Gáborné Jakab Ágnes, Jakab Erika, Bányai Tamás, Kormondi Sándor, Tóth Mihály, and Vrancsik László. The bottom of the screen shows the Windows taskbar with the time 11:26.

Panel discussion about how to strengthen knowledge transfer network

